

6G MULTiband Wireless and Optical Signalling for Integrated CommunicAtions, Sensing and Localization

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D4.3 “Multistatic Sensing and Resource Allocation Mechanisms Network”

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Executive Summary

6G-MUSICAL is an ambitious European research project under the Smart Network Services Joint Undertaking (SNS-JU), aimed at transforming the future of wireless communication and sensing in 6G networks. The project pioneers the seamless integration of radio frequency (RF) communication and radar-based sensing technologies, enabling highly accurate localisation and object tracking at the network edge. By developing energy and spectrum-efficient systems, 6G-MUSICAL will support next-generation services that require both high-speed communication and precise environmental awareness. Unlike other initiatives, the project uniquely focuses on detecting both connected and non-connected objects, expanding the reach of network intelligence, and addresses the critical challenge of synchronising distributed edge nodes for ultra-high accuracy. Leveraging cutting-edge optical and electronic technologies, the project will build a network of intelligent, cooperative radars, supporting new services such as high-precision localisation and advanced 3D mapping. Machine learning (ML) will optimise system performance and service delivery across wireless, network, and hardware domains. Key technologies will be demonstrated in laboratory environments to validate their performance against rigorous targets, paving the way for the next generation of intelligent, energy-efficient, and highly capable 6G networks.

The 6G-MUSICAL project is structured into seven work packages (WP1–7), each targeting specific project goals. WP4, titled “Network Synchronisation, Cloud Radio Sensing, and Resource Allocation,” is composed of four key Tasks (Tasks 4.1–4.4). Together, these tasks address three core objectives of the project:

- Design and develop low-noise, highly stable reference sources for RF carrier generation and timing synchronisation.
- Develop and validate cooperative multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) multistatic sensing algorithms to enable high-accuracy localisation, object tracking, and high-resolution 3D imaging.
- Create dynamic resource allocation strategies to optimise radio resources for localisation, sensing, and communication.

This deliverable, D4.3, focuses on activities within Tasks 4.3 and 4.4 and provides an intermediate report on:

- Beamforming algorithms for the joint communication and sensing (JCAS) paradigm, aiming to significantly reduce the fronthaul load by distributing the signal processing tasks between the central unit and the access points.
- Signal processing algorithms for multistatic sensing, focusing on signal processing for range, Doppler, angle of arrival (AoA), translation of the results into global Cartesian coordinates, and the impact of time-synchronisation, are highlighted.
- Baseband algorithms in the sensing station level of the multistatic scenario to support centralised high-resolution multistatic sensing functions and a secure sensing mechanism.
- Estimation algorithms to estimate the Doppler frequency and AoA of passive (i.e., unconnected) objects.
- Resource sharing scenarios and their performance evaluation in terms of the Cramér-Rao bound (CRB) associated with AoA and symbol estimation, assuming unitary normalised constant envelope signalling. Establishing the CRB gives important engineering insights for practical AoA and symbol estimation algorithms.
- Transmit signalling design and resource allocation framework for distributed (D-JCAS) systems, integrating both colocated and distributed MIMO radar for target localisation alongside noncoherent coordinated multi-point (CoMP) downlink communication.

- Algorithms for associating sets of access points (APs) to user equipments (UEs) in a JCAS scenario, where the transmitter APs communicate with multiple UEs and simultaneously steer beams toward a target.

Importantly, the activities in WP4 are closely linked to the use cases and system requirements defined in WP2. The design approaches developed in Tasks 4.3 and 4.4 are guided by the practical scenarios and performance expectations identified in WP2. The outcome of Tasks 4.3 and 4.4 will play a crucial role in the success of 6G-MUSICAL, namely for the OpenWiFi demonstrator developed in WP6.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full Form
ADMM	Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicles
AoA	Angle of Arrival
AoD	Angle of Departure
AP	Access Point
ASIC	Application-Specific Integrated Circuit
AWGN	Additive White Gaussian Noise
BCRB	Bayesian Cramér-Rao Bound
BPSK	Binary Phase Shift Keying
BS	Base Station
CDF	Cumulative Distribution Function
CF	Cell-Free
CIR	Channel Impulse Response
CoMP	Coordinated Multi-point
CP	Cyclic Prefix
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRB	Cramér-Rao Bound
CRLB	Cramér-Rao Lower Bound
CSI	Channel State Information
CSIR	Channel State Information at the Receiver
CSIT	Channel State Information at the Transmitter
CU	Central Unit
DFT	Discrete Fourier Transform
D-JCAS	Distributed JACS
EHT	Extremely High Throughput
ER	Enhanced Recovery
EU	User Equipment
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
FIR	Finite Impulse Filter
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Arrays
HE	High Efficiency
HT	High Throughput
IFFT	Inverse Fast Fourier Transform
IQ	In-phase and Quadrature
JCAS	Joint Communication and Sensing
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LoS	Line of Sight
LS	Least Square
LTF	Long Training Frame
MAC	Medium Access Control
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
ML	Machine Learning
MM	Majorization-Minimization
MMSE	Minimum Mean Square Error
MRC	Maximum Ratio Combining
MSE	Mean Squared Error

MU	Multi-User
MUI	Multi-User-Interference
NS	Null-Space
OFDM	Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing
PDF	Probability Density Function
PER	Packet Error Rate
PHY	Physical Layer
PoC	Proof of Concept
PPDU	Physical layer Protocol Data Unit
PSD	Power Spectral Density
PVPRs	Probability of Varying Price Rejections
QoS	Quality of Service
RCS	Radar Cross Section
RF	Radio Frequency
SDR	Software Defined Radio
SINR	Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SNS JU	Smart Network Services Joint Undertaking
SU	Single-User
SVD	Singular Value Decomposition
TB	Trigger-Based
TO	Time-Offset
ToA	Time of Arrival
TOF	Time-of-Flight
TRP	Transmission and Reception Point
TsDBA	Two-stage Distributed Beamforming Algorithm
UAVs	Unmanned Aerial Vehicles
UE	User Equipment
ULAs	Uniform Linear Array
UMAC	Upper MAC
VHT	Very High Throughput
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

WP4 of the 6G-MUSICAL project is dedicated to developing key mechanisms and algorithms to enable multistatic sensing and localisation in a cell-free network environment. It specifically tackles the challenge of time-frequency synchronization between nodes, which is vital for efficient multistatic sensing. The work package also develops algorithms for the joint processing of sensing data across various nodes. Furthermore, WP4 aims to optimize resource allocation to improve sensing and localization performance the context of cell-free (CF).

This deliverable specifically encompasses Tasks 4.3 and 4.4 and focus on the design of multistatic and efficient resource allocation algorithms for radio-sensing and positioning. Specifically,

Task 4.3, *“Multistatic Sensing for 3D Imaging and Object Identification”*, is led by IT with the participation of IMEC, and ETL. This task follows the specifications issued in WP2 and aims at the signal design and joint receiver/transmitter processing for the case where we have multiple nodes forming a radio sensing multistatic radar, and for communications, several cells centred at the user. It also focuses on 3D object reconstruction or imaging, and identification. The scope includes both connected and unconnected objects. This task involves designing a transceiver algorithm that strikes a balance between communication performance, sensing accuracy, and privacy protection capability for use in the OpenWiFi demonstrator in Task 6.1. This leads to designing high-resolution, non-biased sensing algorithms with limited degradation of communication performance. An authorised sensing mechanism where the transmitter algorithm restricts the sensing task to authorised receivers by incorporating a channel state information (CSI) fuzzer inside the transmitter, and joint optimisation of sensing, privacy protection (CSI fuzzer), and communication performance.

Task 4.4, *“Intelligent Resource Allocation Mechanisms and Self-Organization of Cell-Free Radio Sensing”*, is led by ETL with the participation of IT and UCL. In this task, we investigate and define efficient resource allocation algorithms for radio-sensing and positioning. In this task, we also investigate setting the needed requirements, taking into account the practical limitations of the OpenWiFi demonstrator in Task 6.1, to come up with a set of feasible and realistic specs. JCAS systems must form beams for both communication, based on accurate or imperfect channel state information at the transmitter (CSIT), and sensing, which lacks prior target knowledge. This requires handling differing beamforming needs using shared resources (time slots, frequency channels, transmit power, antenna and RF chain resources, etc.). Receiver performance also hinges on channel state information at the receiver (CSIR) and resource allocation. Therefore, this task aims to model and optimize these trade-offs, developing practical resource allocation strategies that ensure high-quality sensing with minimal impact on communication performance.

1.2 Overview and Organisation of the Document

The rest of the document is organised as follows,

Section 2 designs a two-stage beamforming algorithm for the CF JCAS paradigm, aiming to significantly reduce the fronthaul load by distributing the signal processing tasks between the central unit (CU) and the access points. The algorithm explicitly incorporates both communication and sensing requirements into the optimization process, addressing power and signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) constraints in a cell-free JCAS context.

Section 3 discusses different aspects of signal processing algorithms associated with multistatic sensing, considering orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) as a reference baseband waveform and beamforming at the transmitter and receiving nodes. Specifically focusing, signal

processing for range, Doppler, angle of arrival, translation of the results into global Cartesian coordinates, and impact of time-synchronization is highlighted.

Section 4 enters the sensing station level and addresses that the traditional communication nodes are not suitable to act as a sensing station due to the limited resolution as the result of the extreme optimization for communication performance and footprint. The section proposes the architectural design and processing algorithms at the single station level to bring the high-resolution sensing data collection and secure sensing mechanism, which is essential for the centralized multistatic sensing algorithm. The simulation and the actual measurement on the modified OpenWiFi (full-stack 802.11 field programmable gate arrays (FPGA) implementation) platform demonstrate the effectiveness.

Section 5 addresses the challenge of estimating the Doppler frequency and angle of arrival of a passive object. The estimation process uses noisy sensing signals received at multiple time instances as input, and outputs the estimated angle and Doppler frequency, either locally at individual sensing nodes or centrally at a fusion entity. Within this general framework of multiple transmission and reception points (multi-TRP) networks, the section analyses how key system parameters, such as the number of receiving access points and the number of available time samples, influence estimation accuracy.

Section 6 we study the three resource sharing scenarios and compare their performance in terms of the CRB associated with AoA and symbol estimation, assuming unitary normalized constant envelope signalling. Establishing the CRB provides important engineering insights and serves as benchmarks for practical algorithms in positioning unconnected objects across various use cases, including intruder localisation in secure areas and the localisation of unconnected or unauthorised unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs).

Section 7 proposes an innovative transmit signalling design and resource allocation framework for D-JCAS systems, integrating both colocated and distributed MIMO radar for target localisation alongside noncoherent CoMP downlink communication. The sensing component adopts a hybrid localisation strategy that combines AoA and time-of-flight (TOF) measurements, effectively leveraging the strengths of both techniques to enable high-precision target localisation.

In Section 8, we discuss algorithms for associating sets of APs to UEs in a JCAS scenario, where the transmitter APs communicate with multiple UEs and simultaneously steer beams toward a target. First, we propose a simple association scheme in which AP–UE pairing is performed randomly. The second algorithm uses the channel norm as a metric to perform the association between APs and UEs. Finally, the third scheme assigns a fixed number of UEs, with the highest channel norms, to each AP. It is worth noting that this work presents preliminary results on intelligent resource allocation, and optimised methods are foreseen for the following reports.

Section 9 concludes this deliverable.

Notation: Capital boldface letters denote matrices; lower boldface letters denote column vectors, and italics denote scalars and symbols.

2 Two-Stage Distributed Beamforming Design in Cell-Free Massive MIMO JCAS Systems

This section presents a two-stage beamforming algorithm for the CF JCAS paradigm, aiming to significantly reduce the fronthaul load by distributing the signal processing tasks between the CU and the APs. The design optimises the sum signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) for communication users, subject to per-AP power constraints and SNR requirements for radio-sensing purposes. The resulting optimisation problems are non-convex and challenging to solve. To address this, we employ a majorization-minimisation (MM) approach, which decomposes the problem into simpler convex subproblems.

2.1 Motivation and Objectives

Distributed JCAS architectures have attracted growing attention due to their improved coverage, diversity, resilience to shadowing, and robustness to environmental dynamics. These benefits have led to various precoding strategies tailored to different system objectives [1]-[5]. In [1], transmit beamforming was designed to maximize sensing SNR under SINR and per-AP power constraints in a CF JCAS setup. The work in [2] analysed the trade-off region among communication-only, sensing-only, and joint beamforming designs. [3] further advanced the field by jointly optimizing transmit and receive beamformers along with AP mode selection, maximizing sensing SNR under power, SINR, and mode constraints. Unlike these sensing-centric approaches, [4] proposed a communication-centric formulation that prioritizes communication rate while ensuring radar estimation and power requirements. Finally, [5] introduced a hybrid beamforming solution based on ADMM, distributing processing between the central unit and APs to reduce central complexity, though at the cost of increased fronthaul usage.

Previous contributions to CF JCAS beamforming design typically require high-capacity fronthaul links and centralized processing, which hinder scalability in dense networks. In contrast, this work proposes a distributed approach that alleviates fronthaul load and computational complexity, enabling more efficient and scalable CF JCAS deployment.

The work aligns with the objectives of Task 4.3, which focuses on the signal design for the case there are multiple nodes forming for radio-sensing a multistatic radar and for communication several APs centred at the user. In line with this, the design implements a two-stage beamforming scheme, where the CU performs an initial layer of precoding, and the APs locally refine the beamforming vectors. The algorithm explicitly incorporates both communication and sensing requirements into the optimization process, addressing power and SNR constraints in a cell-free JCAS context. This distributed architecture enables a more scalable and efficient signal processing solution, significantly reducing fronthaul load and computational complexity in the CU. This approach reflects the core goals of Task 4.3, namely designing transceiver algorithms that addresses and appropriate balance between communication performance and sensing accuracy. The following sections present the system model and provide a detailed description of the proposed algorithm.

The distributed beamforming strategy proposed for cell-free JCAS systems in this document contributes directly to multiple 6G-MUSICAL use cases by enabling energy-efficient, scalable, and localisation-aware joint sensing and communication. The proposed algorithm is particularly well-suited for Indoor automated guided vehicle (AGV) Localisation (Use Case 6.1.1 in D2.1), where accurate spatial resolution is essential. By coordinating distributed APs to generate coherent beams with sub-meter angular and range precision, the method ensures reliable localisation of AGVs in warehouse and production facilities. The cooperation among APs enhances spatial diversity, which is key to improving localisation accuracy. In addition, real-time operation is achieved through local processing at the APs, while the distributed nature of the algorithm contributes to a more scalable and flexible system design.

For Weather Monitoring (Use Case 6.3.1 in D2.1), the ability to steer a centralised probing beam from distributed transmitters and coherently combine returns from spatially dispersed receivers allows the system to detect environmental conditions such as localised precipitation or microclimate shifts with high spatial granularity.

Furthermore, the probing-based sensing model employed in the algorithm ensures robust radar illumination for Intruder Detection (Use Case 6.2.1 in D2.1) and UAV Monitoring (Use Case 6.2.3 in D2.1). These use cases require exploiting the diversity provided by cooperative APs to guarantee reliable detection under varying interference and mobility conditions. The proposed method supports this by jointly optimising the transmitted waveforms across APs and ensuring that the target sensing SNR remains above a predefined threshold. This helps maintain critical key performance indicators (KPIs), such as keeping the intruder miss-detection probability below 2%. The coordinated design increases the system's degrees of freedom, thereby enhancing sensing robustness in secure or high-risk environments.

2.2 System Model

Figure 2.1 illustrates the considered CF JCAS scenario where the APs are divided into M transmitters (AP_{tx}) and N receivers (AP_{rx}). These APs are connected to the CU via fronthaul links. The set of AP_{tx}/AP_{rx} forms a multistatic topology within the CF JCAS scenario, which enables radio-sensing applications. Figure 2.1. Also, AP_{tx} and AP_{rx} hold uniform linear arrays (ULAs) with N_{tx} and N_{rx} antenna elements, respectively.

Figure 2.1: Illustration of the considered CF JCAS scenario.

This work considers a scenario where the set of AP_{tx} communicates in the downlink with K single-antenna UEs, while simultaneously steering a single probing beam in the desired direction for target detection and estimation. Additionally, the set of AP_{rx} is configured to function exclusively as radio-sensing receivers. Specifically, the signals received by the AP_{rx} are processed to detect and estimate objects in the environment.

We make the following assumptions about the CF JCAS scenario:

- 1) each UE is connected to all AP_{tx} ,

- 2) all AP_{tx} steer their radio-sensing beam towards the same geographic location (a point-like target, as shown in Figure 2.1).

Additionally, we consider that all APs are synchronized and that the CSI between the AP_{tx} and the UEs is perfectly known by the AP_{tx}. We emphasize that each AP_{tx} has knowledge only of its local channel to the UEs, and not the channels of other AP_{tx} to the UEs.

Regarding the radio-sensing function, the set of AP_{tx}/AP_{rx} cooperatively scan the environment under the orchestration of the CU. For this, the CU calculates the angles corresponding to a specific position where an alleged target might be located and forwards this information to the APs, allowing them to direct the radio-sensing beams toward that position. Additionally, both the AP_{tx} and AP_{rx} have a line of sight (LoS) to the target, though a LoS path between the AP_{tx} and AP_{rx} is not required.

2.2.1 Transmitted Signal Model

This subsection presents the joint communication and radio-sensing signal model used in the downlink transmissions. More specifically, each AP_{tx} transmits K data streams towards the UEs, where the communication data streams are also used for radio-sensing purposes [7]-[9]. The signal transmitted by the m th AP_{tx} is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}_m &= \mathbf{F}_m \mathbf{s} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{f}_{m,k} s_k \end{aligned} \quad (2.1)$$

where $\mathbf{f}_{m,k} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{tx}}}$ represents the beamforming vector corresponding to the k th data stream, and $\mathbf{s} = [s_1, \dots, s_K]^T$ is the vector of the communication symbols. The AP_{tx} and the CU coordinate to design the precoders \mathbf{F}_m , with the assumption that the CSI is perfectly estimated and locally known by each AP_{tx}. The transmitted data streams s_k are independent and have unit power, i.e., $\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{s}\mathbf{s}^H] = \mathbf{I}_K$. Additionally, the power budget for the beamforming vector is constrained by P_m , formally

$$\|\mathbf{F}_m\|_F^2 \leq P_m. \quad (2.2)$$

2.2.2 Communication Model

As previously mentioned, the transmission of communication data follows a CF approach. Consequently, the signal received by the k th UE is modeled as the sum of the signals transmitted by the M AP_{tx}, as described in (2.1). The received signal y_k is given by

$$y_k = \underbrace{\sum_{m=1}^M \mathbf{h}_{m,k}^H \mathbf{f}_{m,k} s_k}_{\text{Desired Signal (DS)}} + \underbrace{\sum_{i=1, i \neq k}^K \sum_{m=1}^M \mathbf{h}_{m,k}^H \mathbf{f}_{m,i} s_i}_{\text{Multi-user Interference (MUI)}} + \underbrace{n_k}_{\text{Noise}} \quad (2.3)$$

where $n_k \sim \text{CN}(0, \sigma_k^2)$ represents complex additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) with zero mean and variance σ_k^2 . The term $\mathbf{h}_{m,k} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{tx}}}$ denotes the communication channel between the m th AP_{tx} and the k th UE.

The communication channel $\mathbf{h}_{m,k}$ is modeled as a narrowband block-fading propagation channel, as described in [10]. Formally, it is expressed as

$$\mathbf{h}_{m,k} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{L}} \sum_{l=1}^L \alpha_{m,k}^{(l)} \mathbf{a}_{N_{\text{tx}}}(\psi_{m,k}^{(l)}) \quad (2.4)$$

where L is the number of paths, $\alpha_{m,k}^{(l)}$ represents the channel gain, and $\mathbf{a}_{N_{\text{tx}}}(\psi_{m,k}^{(l)})$ represents the transmit array response vector of the l th path, with $\psi_{m,k}^{(l)}$ denoting the angle of departure (AoD). Building on the established conditions of independence among data streams and between the data streams and receiver noise, we can now derive the total power of the received signal in (2.3). Under these assumptions, the total power of the received signal in (2.3) can be derived as

$$\begin{aligned} E[|y_k|^2] &= E[|DS|^2] + E[|MUI|^2] + E[|\text{Noise}|^2] \\ &= P_{\text{DS},k} + P_{\text{MUI},k} + \sigma_k^2, \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

where,

$$P_{\text{DS},k} = \left| \sum_{m=1}^M \mathbf{h}_{m,k}^H \mathbf{f}_{m,k} \right|^2, \quad (2.6)$$

and

$$P_{\text{MUI},k} = \sum_{i=1, i \neq k}^K \left| \sum_{m=1}^M \mathbf{h}_{m,k}^H \mathbf{f}_{m,i} \right|^2. \quad (2.7)$$

Using this decomposition, the SINR at the k th UE is given by

$$\text{SINR}_k = \frac{P_{\text{DS},k}}{P_{\text{MUI},k} + \sigma_k^2}. \quad (2.8)$$

Here, the numerator corresponds to the power of the desired signal received by the k th UE, while the denominator accounts for the total interference from other users and the noise power at the receiver.

2.2.3 Radio-Sensing Model

This work considers a multi-static radar configuration, where the AP_{tx}s direct a radio-sensing probing beam in the direction of a point-like target. It is assumed that a LoS path exists both from the AP_{tx} to the target and from the target to the AP_{rx}. Additionally, the channel between any AP_{tx} and AP_{rx} pair is restricted to this combination of LoS paths. Therefore, the channel between the m th AP_{tx} and the n th AP_{rx} consists of a single path [1], as shown in Figure 2.1. The signal received at the n th AP_{rx} is given by

$$\mathbf{y}_n = \sum_m \hat{\alpha}_{m,n} \mathbf{a}_{N_{\text{rx}}}(\phi_n) \mathbf{a}_{N_{\text{tx}}}^H(\theta_m) \mathbf{x}_m + \mathbf{n}_n \quad (2.9)$$

where $\hat{\alpha}_{m,n}$ is the path gain, which includes the effect of the path-loss, and radar cross section (RCS) of the target [1]. The variables θ_m and ϕ_n represent the AoD from the m th AP_{tx} and the angle of arrival (AoA) at the n th AP_{rx}, respectively. The signals received through the N_{rx} antennas of the n th AP_{rx} are locally combined as follows

$$\begin{aligned} y_n &= \mathbf{g}_n^H \mathbf{y}_n \\ &= \gamma_n \sum_m \hat{\alpha}_{m,n} \mathbf{a}_{N_{\text{tx}}}^H(\theta_m) \mathbf{F}_m \mathbf{s} + \mathbf{g}_n^H \mathbf{n}_n, \end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

where $\mathbf{g}_n \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{rx}}}$ represents the n th combiner, and $\gamma_n = \mathbf{g}_n^H \mathbf{a}(\phi_n)$. The signals in (2.10), from the N AP_{rx},

are forwarded to the CU and coherently added. Thus, the signal at the CU is given by

$$y = \sum_n \sum_m \gamma_n \hat{\alpha}_{m,n} \mathbf{a}_{N_{\text{tx}}}^H(\theta_m) \mathbf{F}_m \mathbf{s} + \sum_n \mathbf{g}_n^H \mathbf{n}_n. \quad (2.11)$$

We consider that the noise at different AP_{tx} are independent and identically distributed (*i.i.d.*) random variables. In addition, we employ the Swerling I model, which is useful for modeling targets with multiple scattering elements, where the scatterings between different transmitter/receiver pairs are independent [1]. That means that there is no correlation between $\hat{\alpha}_{m,n}$ for the different AP_{tx,m}/AP_{tx,n} pairs. Consequently, the expected power of (2.11) can be obtained as

$$E[|y|^2] = \sum_m \sum_n \sigma_{m,n}^2 \|\gamma_n \hat{\alpha}_{m,n} \mathbf{a}_{N_{\text{tx}}}^H(\theta_m) \mathbf{F}_m\|_F^2 + \sum_n \|\mathbf{g}_n\|^2 \sigma_n^2. \quad (2.12)$$

From the above, it follows that the sensing SNR (sSNR) is given by

$$\text{sSNR} = \frac{\sum_m \sum_n \sigma_{m,n}^2 \|\gamma_n \hat{\alpha}_{m,n} \mathbf{a}_{N_{\text{tx}}}^H(\theta_m) \mathbf{F}_m\|_F^2}{\sum_n \|\mathbf{g}_n\|^2 \sigma_n^2}, \quad (2.13)$$

where $\sigma_{m,n}^2$ denotes the variance of the sensing channel.

2.3 Algorithm Description

In prior work on beamforming design for CF JCAS [1]-[4], the computation of the precoders is entirely performed at the CU, requiring significant data exchange between the AP_{tx}s and the CU. In this setup, the AP_{tx}s function as distributed antennas, leading to two main drawbacks. First, the computational complexity at the CU is increased due to the high dimensionality of the optimization variables. Second, fronthaul capacity limitations arise, as the CSI must be transmitted from the AP_{tx}s to the CU for beamforming design, followed by the transmission of the precoding matrices or signals from the CU back to the AP_{tx}s.

To mitigate these drawbacks, this section introduces a distributed beamforming framework in which the precoding vectors $\mathbf{f}_{m,k} \forall m,k$ are divided into two parts. Specifically, we define these precoding vectors as follows

$$\mathbf{f}_{m,k} = \delta_{m,k} \mathbf{w}_{m,k}, \quad (2.14)$$

where $\mathbf{w}_{m,k} \in C^{N_{\text{tx}}}$ represents the local precoding vector, computed at each AP_{tx}, and $\delta_{m,k}$ is a complex weight computed at the CU. Figure 2.2 illustrates how the transmitted signal is formed. In the following, any reference to the precoder design refers to the design of the distributed beamforming framework. The formulation up to this point can be straightforwardly rewritten by simply substituting (2.14).

As depicted in Figure 2.2, the data stream vector \mathbf{s} is precoded at the CU using M diagonal precoding matrices.

The resulting signals are then transmitted through the fronthaul to each of the M AP_{tx}. Formally, the signal sent from the CU to the m th AP_{tx} is given by

$$\mathbf{s}_m = \mathbf{\Delta}_m \mathbf{s}, \quad (2.15)$$

where $\mathbf{\Delta}_m = \text{diag}\{\delta_{m,1}, \dots, \delta_{m,K}\} \in C^{K \times K}$ represents the central precoding matrix of the m th AP_{tx} processed by the CU. Then, (2.15) is precoded using a local precoding matrix by each AP_{tx}. Therefore, the

transmitted signal (2.1) from the m th AP_{tx} can be reformulated as

$$\mathbf{x}_m = \mathbf{W}_m \mathbf{s}_m, \quad (2.16)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_m \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{tx}} \times K}$ is the precoder corresponding to the m th AP_{tx} . From (2.15) and (2.16), it follows that $\mathbf{F}_m = \mathbf{W}_m \mathbf{\Delta}_m$.

Figure 2.2: Diagram of the generation of the transmitted signal in a distributed paradigm within CF JCAS.

The problem is formulated as the maximization of the sum of the SINR (2.8) for the UEs, subject to the power budget for each AP_{tx} and the minimum sSNR requirements for radio-sensing purposes. However, the proposed optimization problem is a challenging and computationally expensive nonconvex problem. To address this, we introduce a solution based on cancelling the inter-user interference. The interference-free precoders are designed in a two-stage distributed manner between the AP_{tx} s and the CU. However, both problems to be solved at the AP_{tx} s and the CU remain non-convex. Therefore, we leverage a MM framework to obtain a simpler lower-bound surrogate function, from which an iterative optimization algorithm can be derived to approximate a solution to the original problem.

2.3.1 Problem Formulation

The objective of this work is to design $\mathbf{\Delta}_m$, and \mathbf{W}_m that maximize the sum of the downlink SINR for the K UEs in a CF JCAS system, considering a multi-user (MU) and single-target scenario. The solution must satisfy two constraints; the power budget per AP_{tx} , and the sSNR in (2.13) must be greater than the minimum value. Consequently, the optimization problem can be formulated as follows

$$\max_{\{\mathbf{W}_m, \mathbf{\Delta}_m\}_m} \sum_k \text{SINR}_k \quad (2.17a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \|\mathbf{W}_m \mathbf{\Delta}_m\|_F^2 \leq P_m, \quad \forall m \quad (2.17b)$$

$$\text{sSNR} \geq \Delta \quad (2.17c)$$

where P_m denotes the available power budget at the m th AP_{tx} , and Δ represents the minimum threshold for the sSNR. This threshold is crucial for ensuring that the received signal power is sufficiently strong to enable accurate detection and estimation of the target parameters.

The MUI in (2.8) significantly increases the complexity of (2.17), making it computationally expensive to find a solution. This complexity arises from the need to jointly account for the interference among multiple users, which complicates the maximization of the SINR objective function in a CF scenario. To address this challenge, we propose a solution that simplifies the optimization problem by cancelling the MUI. This approach effectively reduces the dimensionality of the optimization problem, allowing for a more tractable solution.

2.3.2 Interference Cancellation via Null-space Projection

One approach to eliminate the multi-user interference (MUI) (2.7) between the data streams involves projecting the precoder vectors, i.e., $\mathbf{w}_{m,k} \forall m,k$, into null-space (NS) of the interference channels. This projection is performed locally by each AP_{tx}, without requiring any information exchange between the AP_{tx}s. As a result, the NS-based optimization problem can be reformulated as follows

$$\max_{\{\widehat{\mathbf{W}}_m, \Delta_m\}_m} \sum_k \widehat{P}_{DS,k} \quad (2.18a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_k |\delta_{m,k}|^2 \|\widehat{\mathbf{w}}_{m,k}\|^2 \leq P_m, \forall m \quad (2.18b)$$

$$\sum_m \sum_n \sum_k \sigma_{m,n}^2 |\gamma_n \delta_{m,k} \mathbf{a}_{m,k}^H \widehat{\mathbf{w}}_{m,k}|^2 \geq \widetilde{\Delta}, \quad (2.18c)$$

where

$$\widehat{P}_{DS,k} = \left| \sum_m \delta_{m,k} \widehat{\mathbf{h}}_{m,k}^H \widehat{\mathbf{w}}_{m,k} \right|^2, \quad (2.19)$$

$\widehat{\mathbf{h}}_{m,k}$ and $\mathbf{a}_{m,k}$ are obtained by projecting $\mathbf{h}_{m,k}$ and $\mathbf{a}_{N_{tx}}(\theta_m)$ into the null space of the interference channel $\mathbf{H}_{m,\bar{k}}$, defined as

$$\widehat{\mathbf{h}}_{m,k} = \mathbf{P}_{m,k}^H \mathbf{h}_{m,k}, \quad (2.20)$$

$$\mathbf{a}_{m,k} = \mathbf{P}_{m,k}^H \mathbf{a}_{N_{tx}}(\theta_m)$$

where $\mathbf{P}_{m,k} = \text{null}(\mathbf{H}_{m,\bar{k}})$ represents an orthonormal basis spanning the null space of the interference channel

$$\mathbf{H}_{m,\bar{k}} \triangleq [\mathbf{h}_{m,1}, \dots, \mathbf{h}_{m,k-1}, \mathbf{h}_{m,k+1}, \dots, \mathbf{h}_{m,K}]^H. \quad (2.21)$$

Moreover, $\widehat{\mathbf{w}}_{m,k}$ denotes the projected precoder, from which $\mathbf{w}_{m,k} = \mathbf{P}_{m,k} \widehat{\mathbf{w}}_{m,k}$ follows, and $\widetilde{\Delta} = \sum_n \|\mathbf{g}_n\|^2 \sigma_n^2 \Delta$.

2.3.3 Iterative Two-stage Distributed Beamforming Design Algorithm

The design of $\widehat{\mathbf{W}}_m$ and Δ_m is realized in a distributed manner, where the $\widehat{\mathbf{W}}_m$ are computed in parallel across the M AP_{tx}s, and Δ_m is determined at the CU. The data exchange flow between the AP_{tx}s and the CU is illustrated in Figure 2.3. Note that the presented schematic is conceptual, emphasizing the data generated by each entity rather than the physical architecture, which can be implemented using various topologies, such as star, mesh, or tree.

Figure 2.3: High-level schematic of the data exchange required for the two-stage distributed beamforming design algorithm.

At the m th AP_{tx}, $\widehat{\mathbf{W}}_m$ is computed using information sent by the CU, including the $\delta_{m,k}$ weights specific to that AP_{tx}. Additionally, data from the other $M - 1$ AP_{tx}s is required, such as the $\alpha_{m,k}$ and $\beta_{m,k}$ values, which represent the equivalent communication and radio-sensing channels, which accounts local and central precoding, respectively. We want to highlight that the computed precoders remain local to each AP_{tx}, and only partial information is forwarded to the CU. The CU computes the $\delta_{m,k}$ weights using partial information from the AP_{tx}, such as $z_{m,k}$ and $g_{m,k}$, which represent the equivalent local communication and radio-sensing channels, respectively. Additionally, $w_{m,k}$ denotes the power of $\widehat{\mathbf{W}}_{m,k}$. The data exchange between AP_{tx} and CU continues iteratively until the number of iterations N_{iter} is reached.

2.3.4 Local Precoder Optimization at the m th AP_{tx}

As previously mentioned, the optimization of $\widehat{\mathbf{w}}_{m,k} \forall k$ is performed by the m th AP_{tx}, requiring partial information from the other AP_{tx}s and the CU. This problem is the same across all AP_{tx}s, allowing each to be resolved independently and in parallel. Therefore, the optimization problem at the m th AP_{tx} is given by

$$\max_{\{\widehat{\mathbf{w}}_{m,k}\}_k} \sum_k \left| \delta_{m,k} \mathbf{h}_{m,k}^H \widehat{\mathbf{w}}_{m,k} + \sum_{i \neq m} \alpha_{i,k} \right|^2 \quad (2.22a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_k |\delta_{m,k}|^2 \|\widehat{\mathbf{w}}_{m,k}\|^2 \leq P_m \quad (2.22b)$$

$$\sum_k \sum_n \sigma_{m,n}^2 |\gamma_n \delta_{m,k} \mathbf{a}_{m,k}^H \widehat{\mathbf{w}}_{m,k}|^2 + \sum_{i \neq m} \sum_k \sum_n \sigma_{i,n}^2 |\gamma_n \beta_{i,k}|^2 \geq \widetilde{\Delta}, \quad (2.22c)$$

where $\alpha_{i,k} = \delta_{i,k} z_{i,k}$ represents the equivalent communication channel, accounting for both central and local precoding. Here, $z_{i,k}$ denotes the equivalent local communication channel for the other AP_{tx}s,

formally defined as $z_{i,k} = \hat{\mathbf{h}}_{i,k}^H \hat{\mathbf{w}}_{i,k}$. In the same way, $\beta_{i,k} = \delta_{i,k} g_{i,k}$ is the equivalent radio-sensing channel, accounting for both central and local precoding. The term $g_{i,k}$ refers to the local radio-sensing channel for the remaining AP_{tx}s, defined as $g_{i,k} = \mathbf{a}_{i,k}^H \hat{\mathbf{w}}_{i,k}$.

The optimization problem (2.22) is non-convex due to the nature of the objective function and the radio-sensing related constraint (2.22c). The maximization objective (2.22a) aims to maximize the sum of absolute values, which is a convex function, resulting in a non-convex optimization problem. On the other hand, the constraint in (2.22c) involves the sum of convex quadratic terms, but since the inequality is in the form of a lower bound, it represents the complement of a convex set. As a result, this constraint describes a non-convex region.

An effective approach to addressing the previously nonconvex problem is to leverage a MM framework. This method allows us to generate a sequence of simpler, convex subproblems that are easier to solve, ultimately leading to an approximate solution for the original non-convex problem. The considered surrogate function is represented as the first-order Taylor polynomial of (2.22a). The lower bound surrogate optimization problem can be recast as follows

$$\{\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{m,k}^{(t)}\}_k = \arg \max_{\{\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{m,k}\}_k} 2\Re \left(\sum_k \nabla_{\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{m,k}} \hat{P}_{\text{DS},k}^H(\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{m,k}^{(t-1)}) \hat{\mathbf{w}}_{m,k} \right) \quad (2.23a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_k |\delta_{m,k}|^2 \|\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{m,k}\|^2 \leq P_m, \forall m \quad (2.23b)$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{MNK}} \Re(\sum_k \sum_n \sigma_{m,n} \gamma_n \delta_{m,k} \mathbf{a}_{m,k}^H \hat{\mathbf{w}}_{m,k} + \sum_{i \neq m} \sum_k \sum_n \sigma_{i,n} \gamma_n \beta_{i,k}) \geq \tilde{\Delta}^{1/2} \quad (2.23c)$$

where the operator $\nabla_{\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{m,k}} \hat{P}_{\text{DS},k}$ denotes the gradient of (2.19) with respect to $\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{m,k}$, formally

$$\nabla_{\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{m,k}} \hat{P}_{\text{DS},k} = |\delta_{m,k}|^2 \hat{\mathbf{h}}_{m,k} \hat{\mathbf{h}}_{m,k}^H \hat{\mathbf{w}}_{m,k} + \sum_{i \neq m} \alpha_{i,k} \delta_{m,k}^* \hat{\mathbf{h}}_{m,k}, \quad (2.24)$$

(2.23) serves as a simplified and convex approximation of (2.22). To handle the non-convexity of constraint (2.22c), it was replaced by (2.23c). This new constraint is convex but it is more restrictive since the set defined by this constraint is a subset of (2.22c). The optimal value of the original problem is less than or equal to the value of the new problem, while the solution satisfies the original constraints. The optimization problem (2.23) is now convex and can be efficiently solved using convex optimization solver tools such as CVX [12].

2.3.5 Precoder Optimization at the CU

The values of the local equivalent communication and radio-sensing channels, $z_{m,k}$ and $g_{m,k}$, along with the power of the precoder vectors defined as $w_{m,k} = \|\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{m,k}\|^2$, are transmitted to the CU by the M AP_{tx}. With this information, the CU computes the weights $\delta_{m,k}$ that solve (2.18). Hence, (2.18) can be recast at the CU as

$$\max_{\{\delta_{m,k}\}_{m,k}} \sum_k \left| \sum_m \delta_{m,k} z_{m,k} \right|^2 \quad (2.25a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_k w_{m,k} |\delta_{m,k}|^2 \leq P_m \quad \forall m \quad (2.25b)$$

$$\sum_m \sum_n \sum_k \sigma_{m,n}^2 |\gamma_n \delta_{m,k} g_{m,k}|^2 \geq \tilde{\Delta}, \quad (2.25c)$$

Notice that the (2.25) is similar to (2.22). Hence, the lower-bound surrogate optimization problem can be reformulated as follows

$$\{\delta_{m,k}^{(t)}\}_{m,k} = \arg \max_{\{\delta_{m,k}\}_{m,k}} 2\Re \left(\sum_m \sum_k \nabla_{\delta_{m,k}} \hat{P}_{DS,k}^H (\delta_{m,k}^{(t-1)}) \delta_{m,k} \right) \quad (2.26a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_k w_{m,k} |\delta_{m,k}|^2 \leq P_m \quad \forall m \quad (2.26b)$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{MNK}} \Re \left(\sum_m \sum_n \sum_k \sigma_{m,n} \gamma_n \delta_{m,k} g_{m,k} \right) \geq \tilde{\Delta}^{1/2}, \quad (2.26c)$$

where $\nabla_{\delta_{m,k}} \hat{P}_{DS,k}$ represents the gradient of (2.19) with respect to $\delta_{m,k}$, formally

$$\nabla_{\delta_{m,k}} \hat{P}_{DS,k} = \delta_{m,k} |z_{m,k}|^2 + z_{m,k}^* \sum_{i \neq m} \delta_{i,k} z_{i,k}. \quad (2.27)$$

The optimization problem (2.26) is convex and can be efficiently solved using for example the convex optimization library CVX [12].

2.4 Results

This section demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed two-stage distributed beamforming algorithm (TsDBA). Additionally, the TsDBA is compared to the centralized beamforming solution of (2.18). In the centralized solution, the beamforming design is entirely performed at the CU.

The following results were obtained for a scenario with $M = 4$ AP_{tx}, $N = 2$ AP_{rx}, and $K = 2$ UEs. The angles of the target relative to the M AP_{tx} are $\theta_1 = -15^\circ$, $\theta_2 = 35^\circ$, $\theta_3 = 5^\circ$, and $\theta_4 = 40^\circ$. Similarly, the angles from AP_{rx} are $\phi_1 = 10^\circ$ and $\phi_2 = -20^\circ$. The AP_{tx} and AP_{rx} are equipped with ULAs, holding $N_{tx} = 32$ and $N_{rx} = 32$ antenna elements, respectively, spaced by $\lambda/2$. The communication channel is modeled according to (2.4), with the number of paths set to 10. In addition, $\psi_{m,k}^{(l)}$ is assumed to follow a uniform distribution over the range $[-\pi/2, \pi/2]$, while $\alpha_{m,k}^{(l)}$ follows a complex Gaussian distribution with a mean of zero and unit variance. Regarding the sSNR, the noise variance at the AP_{rx}s is set to $\sigma_n^2 = -20$ dB. In addition, the AP_{rx}s are assumed to know the AoA (i.e., $\phi_n : \forall n$). A maximum ratio combining (MRC) equalizer is employed at the AP_{rx}s primarily for its simplicity; while other selections could be made, the MRC is chosen for its straightforward implementation.

For simplicity, we assume that the variance of $\hat{\alpha}_{m,n} : \forall m, n$ is $\sigma_{m,n}^2 = -10$ dB. Finally, the power budget of the distributed beamforming matrices is set to $P_m = 1 \forall m$. We start by analyzing the convergence of the proposed algorithm, which is illustrated in Figure 2.4 by plotting the mean sum SINR as a function of the number of iterations, with $N_{iter} = 10$ and $\Delta \in \{30, 40\}$ dB. The results represent the mean over 100 random realizations of the communication channels $\mathbf{w}_{m,k} \forall m, k$.

Figure 2.4 shows that the algorithm converges rapidly within the first few iterations, reporting higher sum SINR for the less stringent radio-sensing constraint $\Delta = 30$ dB compared to $\Delta = 40$ dB, which reflects the trade-off between radio-sensing and communication SINR performance. Notably, after just 3 iterations, the algorithm achieves approximately 99% of the maximum value for $\Delta = 30$ dB and around 98% for $\Delta = 40$ dB, indicating that a small number of iterations is sufficient to reach the maximum performance. Thus, 3 iterations is an appropriate choice to balance computational complexity and convergence accuracy.

Figure 2.5 shows the trade-off between the mean of the sum of the SINR and the sSNR constraint Δ . The sum of the SINR is calculated for Δ values ranging from 30 to 44 dB. For the TsDBA, we have set $N_{iter} = 3$, as this was shown to be an appropriate choice.

Figure 2.4: Convergence of TsDBA under radio-sensing constraints for $\Delta \in \{30,40\}$ dB.

Figure 2.5: The trade-off between the sSNR constraint value Δ and the sum of the SINR, for CF-JCAS scenario with $M = 4$, $N = 2$, and $K = 2$.

The results presented in Figure 2.5 indicate that the proposed TsDBA solution demonstrates a performance close to the centralized solution. Also, both solutions exhibit a decreasing trend in mean sum SINR as Δ increases. This trend highlights a trade-off between the radio-sensing constraints and the achievable sum SINR. Although the centralized solution slightly outperforms the TsDBA across Δ values, the TsDBA significantly reduces fronthaul load requirements.

Figure 2.6 compares the fronthaul load required for beamforming design between the centralized and TsDBA solutions as a function of N_{tx} . The results were obtained using $N_{iter} = 3$, with $M \in \{4,16\}$ AP_{tx} and $K \in \{2,8\}$ UEs.

Figure 2.6: Fronthaul load comparison for beamforming design between the TsDBA and centralized solutions.

From Figure 2.6, it can be noticed that the fronthaul load of the centralized solution increases with N_{tx} , leading to significant data transmission demands between the AP_{tx} s and the CU. In contrast, the TsDBA demonstrates a flat curve, indicating that the fronthaul load remains constant, regardless of N_{tx} . This difference arises because, in the TsDBA, the AP_{tx} s transmit equivalent communication and radio-sensing channels to the CU, rather than the full CSI required by the centralized solution.

2.5 Future Work

In this section, we propose a two-stage distributed beamforming algorithm for cell-free JCAS systems. The approach enables coherent joint sensing and communication across distributed APs, while satisfying per-node power constraints and ensuring minimum sensing SNR at the target. In our future work, we will address practical system limitations not covered in this study. In particular, we will investigate the effects of imperfect CSI and synchronization on the performance of distributed beamforming, as such impairments are likely in real deployments and can degrade both sensing and communication accuracy. Moreover, we plan to extend the proposed design to support 3D imaging capabilities, which require accurate beam steering in both azimuth and elevation domains. This extension is essential for applications such as UAV monitoring and volumetric sensing in complex environments.

3 Multistatic Sensing for JCAS

3.1 Motivation

JCAS has emerged as a technology to enable several applications envisioned for 6G and beyond [48],[49]. To exploit the wireless communication infrastructure for sensing, separate transmitter and receiver nodes not only avoid issues in full-duplex operation but also improve detection accuracy and extend the coverage area [50],[51]. Figure 3.1 shows a schematic example of a multistatic sensing scenario where nodes AP1-AP3 are transmitters for communication/sensing waveforms and nodes AP4-AP5 are dedicated as sensing receivers.

Benefits associated with the multistatic sensing can be fully utilized if the stringent requirement of common referencing is maintained. Common referencing includes synchronization in time, frequency, and common coordinate system. Synchronization in time and frequency guarantees the range and Doppler shift estimates consistency with the physical round trip distances and velocities of the targets, whereas accurate knowledge of node positioning and orientation are important to preserve spatial coherence of sensing results [52]. Some of the use cases where precise common referencing is an essential requirement are:

- 1) AGVs navigation in warehouses and production facilities,
- 2) Gesture recognition in smart homes,

Traffic monitoring in smart cities which are also included in deliverable D2.1 of 6G-MUSICAL.

Figure 3.1: Multistatic Sensing Scenario in JCAS.

While node orientation and location can be recorded at the time of installation, time-frequency synchronisation remains a challenge.

A simple approach to provide synchronisation for time and frequency is through cable/front haul [53],[54] from a central processing unit, as shown depicted in Figure 3.1. For receiver nodes where fronthaul referencing is not possible due to large separation or in case of disruption of the front haul, wireless synchronization [55],[56] is the alternative approach to sever the referencing issue with limited accuracy yet effective for sensing application which do not require high degree of accuracy and resolution such as **intruder detection** in a prohibitive premises or around the **railway track**, or the **fall incidence of the an elderly person at home**, are few examples which are also listed in deliverable D2.1 of the 6G-MUSICAL.

In the following subsections, different aspects of signal processing algorithms associated with multistatic sensing, considering OFDM as a reference baseband waveform and beamforming at the transmitter and receiving nodes is presented. Specifically focusing, signal processing for range,

Doppler, AoA, translation of the results into global Cartesian coordinates, and impact of time-synchronization is highlighted.

3.2 System Model

In a multistatic sensing scenario involving a transmitter T_x and L receiving nodes R_{x_i} where $i \in [1, L]$, we consider a bistatic pair with transmitter located at $\mathbf{p}_{T_x} = (x_{T_x}, y_{T_x}, z_{T_x})^T$ and i -th receiver located at $\mathbf{p}_{R_{x_i}} = (x_{R_{x_i}}, y_{R_{x_i}}, z_{R_{x_i}})^T$. The antenna array orientation is defined by $\Phi_{T_x} = (\theta_{T_x}, \varphi_{T_x})^T$ for the transmitter and $\Phi_{R_{x_i}} = (\theta_{R_{x_i}}, \varphi_{R_{x_i}})^T$ for the i -th receiver. We denote M and N as the number of antenna elements at the transmitter and receiver nodes respectively. Bistatic distance of a target located at point $\mathbf{p}_q = (x_q, y_q, z_q)^T$ is defined as,

$$d_q(x_q, y_q, z_q) = \|\mathbf{p}_{T_x} - \mathbf{p}_q\| + \|\mathbf{p}_q - \mathbf{p}_{R_{x_i}}\| \quad (3.1)$$

The AoA and AoD, associated with point q in 3-D, are denoted by $\Phi_{R_{x_i}, q} = (\theta_{R_{x_i}, q}, \varphi_{R_{x_i}, q})^T$ and $\Phi_{T_x, q} = (\theta_{T_x, q}, \varphi_{T_x, q})^T$, respectively.

If $s_m(t)$ represents the baseband signal, transmitted by the m -th antenna, which propagates through a radio channel consisting of Q number of distinct targets (modeled as point targets), then the received signal at the n -th antenna of node R_{x_i} can be expressed as,

$$y_{n,m}^i(t) = \sum_{q=1}^Q \alpha_q^i a_m(\Phi_{T_x, q}) b_n(\Phi_{R_{x_i}, q}) s_m(t - \tau_q^i) + \epsilon_n^i(t) \quad (3.2)$$

here $\tau_q^i = (d_q^i - v_q^i t)/c_0$ is the propagation delay (c_0 , being the speed of light in free space), $a_m(\Phi_{T_x, q})$ is the Tx steering vector component, $b_n(\Phi_{R_{x_i}, q})$ is the R_{x_i} steering vector component [57], v_q^i denotes the radial component of the speed of the q -th target with respect to the receiver node R_{x_i} , and $\epsilon_n^i(t)$ represents AWGN. α_q^i is the complex amplitude related to the q -th target.

Considering $s_m(t)$ an OFDM waveform with OFDM symbol duration is T , the subcarrier spacing $\Delta f = \frac{1}{T}$. If \mathcal{N} denotes the number of subcarriers, T_{cp} for CP interval, $T_s = T_{cp} + T$ the effective duration of the OFDM symbol, and \mathcal{M} as the total number of transmitted OFDM symbols, the transmitted OFDM waveform can be represented as [58],

$$s_m(t) = \sum_{\mu=0}^{\mathcal{M}-1} \sum_{u=0}^{\mathcal{N}-1} S(\mu\mathcal{N} + u) e^{(j2\pi u \Delta f (t - \mu T_s))} e^{(-j2\pi u \Delta f T_{cp})} \text{rect}\left(\frac{t - \mu T_s}{T_s}\right) e^{j2\pi f_c t} \quad (3.4)$$

where $S(\mu\mathcal{N} + u)$ is the data symbol which modulates the u -th subcarrier of the μ -th OFDM symbol. $\text{rect}(t)$ in (4) is the rectangular pulse shape and the term $e^{(-j2\pi u \Delta f T_{cp})}$ adjusts the initial phase of the subcarrier caused by the cyclic extension. Using (4) in (2), received signal takes the form

$$y_{n,m}^i(t) = \sum_{q=1}^Q \sum_{\mu=0}^{\mathcal{M}-1} \sum_{u=0}^{\mathcal{N}-1} \alpha_q^i a_m(\Phi_{T_x, q}) b_n(\Phi_{R_{x_i}, q}) S(\mu\mathcal{N} + u) e^{(j2\pi u \Delta f (t - \tau_q^i - \mu T_s - T_{cp}))} \cdot e^{(j2\pi f_c (t - \tau_q^i))} \text{rect}\left(\frac{t - \tau_q^i - \mu T_s}{T_s}\right) + \epsilon_n^i(t). \quad (3.5)$$

After down-conversion the baseband equivalent of (5) is,

$$V_{n,m}^i(t) = \sum_{q=1}^Q \sum_{\mu=0}^{\mathcal{M}-1} \sum_{u=0}^{\mathcal{N}-1} \hat{\alpha}_q^i a_m(\Phi_{T_x, q}) b_n(\Phi_{R_{x_i}, q}) S(\mu\mathcal{N} + u) e^{(j2\pi u \Delta f (t - \tau_q^i - \mu T_s - T_{cp}))}$$

$$\cdot e^{(j2\pi f_c(tv_q^i/c_0))} \text{rect}\left(\frac{t - \tau_q^i - \mu T_s}{T_s}\right) + \hat{\epsilon}_n^i(t), \quad (3.6)$$

where $\hat{\alpha}_q^i = \alpha_q^i e^{(-j2\pi f_c d_q^i)}$ and $\hat{\epsilon}_n^i(t) = \epsilon_n^i(t) e^{(-j2\pi f_c t)}$. Finally, the signal $V_{n,m}^i(t)$ is sampled and, after removal of the CP, converted into the frequency domain by using a discrete Fourier transform (DFT) typically implemented by a fast Fourier transform (FFT),

$$A_{n,m}^i(\mu\mathcal{N} + u) = \sum_{q=1}^Q \hat{\alpha}_q^i a_m(\Phi_{\text{Tx},q}) b_n(\Phi_{\text{Rx},i,q}) S(\mu\mathcal{N} + u) e^{(j2\pi u \Delta f \tau_q^i)} \cdot e^{(j2\pi f_c(tv_q^i/(c_0\mu T_s)))} + Z_n^i(\mu\mathcal{N} + u), \quad (3.7)$$

where $A_{n,m}^i(\mu\mathcal{N} + u)$ is the received data symbol (affected by the channel and AWGN) at the u -th subcarrier of the μ -th OFDM symbol at the n -th receiving antenna, and $Z_n^i(\mu\mathcal{N} + u)$ is the frequency domain equivalent of $\hat{\epsilon}_n^i(t)$.

2-D FFT-Based Sensing

For sensing, the received signal $A_{n,m}^i(\mu\mathcal{N} + u)$ is divided by the transmitted data symbols $S(\mu\mathcal{N} + u)$ and applying the inverse fast Fourier transform (IFFT) operation (along subcarriers) results in peaks corresponding to the delay τ_q^i ,

$$\hat{r}_{n,m}^i(\boldsymbol{\kappa}) = \sum_{q=1}^Q \hat{\alpha}_q^i a_m(\Phi_{\text{Tx},q}) b_n(\Phi_{\text{Rx},i,q}) \cdot \frac{1}{\mathcal{N}} \sum_{u=0}^{\mathcal{N}-1} e^{(j2\pi u \Delta f \tau_q^i)} e^{(j2\pi u \boldsymbol{\kappa} / \mathcal{N})} \cdot e^{(j2\pi f_c(tv_q^i/(c_0\mu T_s)))} + \hat{Z}_n^i(\boldsymbol{\kappa}), \quad (3.8)$$

Where $\boldsymbol{\kappa} = (0, \dots, \mathcal{N} - 1)$ defines the range grid in the RD map, and $\hat{Z}_n^i(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$ represents the noise part. Afterwards, an FFT operation is applied along the slow-time (index μ) to the Doppler estimate,

$$\hat{r}_{n,m}^i(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\varkappa}) = \sum_{\mu=0}^{\mathcal{M}-1} \hat{r}_{n,m}^i(\boldsymbol{\kappa}) e^{(-j2\pi \mu / \mathcal{M})} e^{(j2\pi \mu \boldsymbol{\varkappa} / \mathcal{N})} \quad (3.9)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\varkappa} = (0, \dots, \mathcal{M} - 1)$ defines the Doppler grid in RD map.

The IFFT/FFT operations, for range and speed detection, provide processing gain $G = \mathcal{M}\mathcal{N}$ due to coherent addition of signals.

Subsequently, after combining across antenna dimensions yields

$$\begin{aligned} \rho^i(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\varkappa}, \Theta_t, \Theta_r) &= \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N \hat{r}_{n,m}^i(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\varkappa})(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\varkappa}) w_m(\Theta_t) v_n(\Theta_r) \\ &= \sum_{q=1}^Q \hat{\alpha}_q^i \chi_q(\Theta_t) \Psi_q(\Theta_r) \\ &\cdot \sum_{\mu=0}^{\mathcal{M}-1} \sum_{u=0}^{\mathcal{N}-1} \left(e^{j2\pi u \Delta f \tau_q^i} e^{j\frac{2\pi}{\mathcal{N}} u \boldsymbol{\kappa}} \right) \left(e^{j2\pi f_c t \frac{v_q^i}{c_0 \mu T_s}} e^{-j2\pi \frac{\mu}{\mathcal{M}} \boldsymbol{\varkappa}} \right) + \epsilon(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \Theta_t, \Theta_r) \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} \chi_q(\Theta_t) &= \sum_{m=1}^M a_m(\Phi_{Tx,q}) w_m(\Theta_t) \\ \Psi_q(\Theta_r) &= \sum_{n=1}^N b_n(\Phi_{Rx_i,q}) v_n(\Theta_r) \end{aligned} \tag{3.11}$$

where Θ_t and Θ_r are taken from a set of values that cover the scanning range of AoD and AoA, respectively. In the case of beamforming, the filters $w_m(\Theta_t)$ and $v_n(\Theta_r)$ are chosen as the complex conjugate of the steering vectors $a_m(\Phi_{Tx,q})$ and $b_n(\Phi_{Rx_i,q})$, respectively.

Figure 3.2: Schematic illustration of bistatic sensing signal processing using OFDM waveform and beamforming.

Finally, detection is performed based on the results $\rho^i(\kappa, \kappa, \Theta_t, \Theta_r)$, under a predefined threshold value

$$|\rho^i(\kappa, \kappa, \Theta_t, \Theta_r)|^2 \geq \gamma^i \tag{3.12}$$

where the threshold value γ^i is set against the probability of false alarm detection. The set

$(\kappa_j^i, \kappa_j^i, \Theta_{t,j}^i, \Theta_{r,j}^i)$ is represents the j -th detected target at the i -th receiver node Rx_i .

Figure 3.2 summarises the above explained signal processing involved in range, Doppler, and AoA estimation in a bistatic sensing where transmitting signal is reflected from three point-targets to a receiver node. In this illustration, N_{ry} and N_{rx} represent number of rows (y-axis) and number of columns (x-axis) in antenna array at the receiver side.

3.3 Target Localisation in 3D Space

Estimates (range, Doppler, angle) are not sufficient to locate the target in 3D-space with reference to global coordinates. Converting the spherical coordinates to cartesian coordinates is simple and to make the results especially consistent at different nodes, location coordinates of the receiver nodes and orientation of the receiver antenna array is essential to make necessary transformation. In the following subsections we describe this transformation in bistatic configuration compared to monostatic case.

3.3.1 Monostatic Case

In a monostatic case the conversion of the estimated range and angle estimates into global coordinates is

Figure 3.3: Conversion of local polar coordinates into global Cartesian coordinates in monostatic sensing.

simple as explained in the Figure 3.3 where AoA, antenna orientation, estimated range and location of the receiver node is used to get the estimated global coordinates (x_T, y_T, z_T) of the detected target.

3.3.2 Bistatic Case

Let Q_i represents the number of detected targets at the i -th receiving node Rx_i . The polar coordinates of the j -th detected target at the i -th receiving node Rx_i are denoted as $Y_{Rx_i,j} = (r_{Rx_i,j}, \hat{\Theta}_{Rx_i,j}, \hat{\Phi}_{Rx_i,j})$, with

$$r_{Rx_i,j} = c_0 \kappa_j^i (T/\mathcal{N}). \quad (3.13)$$

As depicted Figure 3.4 $r_{Rx_i,j}$ does not represent the actual range $R_{i,j}$ of the target, instead, it includes an excess part $\Delta R_{i,j}$, which depends on the geometry of the bistatic pair and must be subtracted from $r_{Rx_i,j}$. In case of a monostatic setup, $r_{Rx_i,j}$ is simply twice the actual range $R_{i,j}$ which can be calculated directly as explained in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.4: Relation of actual range of the target with bistatic geometry.

Using the transmitter position \mathbf{p}_{Tx} , the receiver position \mathbf{p}_{Rx_i} and the polar coordinates $\mathbf{Y}_{i,j}$, the excess range $\Delta R_{i,j}$ can be determined using the following relation (a derivation for 2-D case is provided in [59], which we extend to the 3-D case here),

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta R_{i,j} = & \left\{ (\Delta T_{i,j})^2 + (\Delta x_i)^2 + (\Delta y_i)^2 + (\Delta z_i)^2 + 2\Delta T_{i,j} (\Delta x_i \cos(\theta_{Rx_i} - \hat{\theta}_{Rx_i,j}) \right. \\ & \cdot \sin(\phi_{Rx_i} - \hat{\phi}_{Rx_i,j}) + \Delta y_i \sin(\theta_{Rx_i} - \hat{\theta}_{Rx_i,j}) \cos(\phi_{Rx_i} - \hat{\phi}_{Rx_i,j}) \\ & \left. + \Delta z_i \sin(\phi_{Rx_i} - \hat{\phi}_{Rx_i,j}) \right\}^{1/2} \end{aligned} \quad (3.14)$$

where

$$\Delta T_{i,j} = \frac{(r_{Rx_i,j})^2 - (\Delta x_i)^2 - (\Delta y_i)^2 - (\Delta z_i)^2}{2 \left(\left(r_{Rx_i,j} + \Delta x_i \cos(\theta_{Rx_i} - \theta_{Rx_i,j}) \cos(\phi_{Rx_i} - \phi_{Rx_i,j}) \right) \right.} \quad (3.15)$$

$$\left. + \Delta y_i \sin(\theta_{Rx_i} - \theta_{Rx_i,j}) \cos(\phi_{Rx_i} - \phi_{Rx_i,j}) + \Delta z_i \sin(\phi_{Rx_i} - \phi_{Rx_i,j}) \right)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta x_i &= x_{Rx_i} - x_{Tx} \\ \Delta y_i &= y_{Rx_i} - y_{Tx} \\ \Delta z_i &= z_{Rx_i} - z_{Tx} \end{aligned} \quad (3.16)$$

Once $\Delta R_{i,j}$ is determined, the actual range of the j -th target is as

$$R_{i,j} = r_{Rx_i,j} - \Delta R_{i,j} \quad (3.17)$$

To convert the local polar coordinates at receiver node Rx_i into the global Cartesian coordinate $(x_{i,j}, y_{i,j}, z_{i,j})^T$ the knowledge of the location and orientation of the receiver node is used as follows. First, use the orientation of the receiver node Rx_i and convert the polar coordinates $(R_{i,j}, \hat{\theta}_{Rx_i,j} + \theta_{Rx_i}, \hat{\phi}_{Rx_i,j} - \phi_{Rx_i})^T$ into Cartesian coordinates $(\hat{x}_{i,j}, \hat{y}_{i,j}, \hat{z}_{i,j})^T$, and then using the location of the receiver mode to get the target position in global coordinates as $\mathbf{p}_{i,j}$ as

$$\mathbf{p}_{i,j} = (\hat{x}_{i,j} + x_{Rx_i}, \hat{y}_{i,j} + y_{Rx_i}, \hat{z}_{i,j} + z_{Rx_i})^T \quad (3.18)$$

3.3.3 Impact of Time-offset

Any Time-offset (TO) between the Tx and Rx_i will affect $r_{Rx_i,j}$ without altering the AoA estimates. Since $r_{Rx_i,j}$ cannot be less than the distance d_{Tx}^i between the Tx and Rx_i , we define $k_{i,j}$ as

$$k_{i,j} = d_{Tx}^i + r_{Rx_{i,j}} - \min_j(r_{Rx_{i,j}}) \quad j \in [1, Q_i] \quad (3.19)$$

and use $k \in [k_{i,j}, L]$ in place of $r_{Rx_{i,j}}$ in (3.14), (3.15), and (3.17) which generates the possible locations of targets due to TO error, where L is the range covered by the CP. In Figure 3.5, a set of four targets (true target locations are shown in red crosses) is shown with possible TO error values. Time offset in bistatic sensing not only displaces the results but also the shape of the detected cluster changes i.e. in case of multistatic sensing for 3-D object identification, time offset error will cause shape deformation (dependency on the geometry of the bistatic configuration has its role as well).

Figure 3.5: Impact of time synchronisation error in bistatic sensing.

3.4 Simulation Results

A multistatic sensing scenario with one transmitter and four receiver nodes, as shown in Figure 3.6 (a), are used for simulation purpose. An OFDM signal is generated using FFT size = 512, and sampling frequency = 1GHz and the waveform is extended with a cyclic prefix (CP) length of 128 samples length before transmission. At each receiver node, range-Doppler and AoA processing is performed using the techniques described in system model. The receiver nodes are equipped with rectangular antenna arrays (8x8) with half-wavelength spacing, and the transmitter with a ULA (1x8). Signal propagation is modelled using a geometrical channel approach, which accounts for the locations of the nodes and point targets. Key simulation parameters are listed in Table 3.1.

In Figure 3.6 (a) a single target located at the centre of the black circle is detected using the four receiver nodes (Rx1-Rx4) which can be distinguished by different colours and their sensing results in matched-coloured dots. Figure 3.6 (b) shows the range, angle estimates of the target at different receiver nodes, enclosed in matched-colour rectangular boxes. The red dot (3-D location estimation of the target from Rx1) shows a larger deviation from the true location, which is caused by the geometry of the Tx and Rx1 (Tx-target-Rx1 are close to a line path).

Table 3.1: Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Sampling frequency F_s	1 GHz	Bandwidth	586 MHz
Carrier frequency f_c	6 GHz	Digital mapping	16 QAM
Active sub-carriers	300	No. of OFDM symbols	16
FFT size	512	Range resolution	0.256 m
Subcarrier spacing Δf	1.953 MHz	Monostatic range (within CP)	16.38 m

Figure 3.6: Multistatic sensing scenario with a single target detected by four receiver nodes.

Figure 3.7: Multistatic sensing for targets arranged in a line in 3-D space.

Figure 3.7 is another simulation result of a multistatic sensing scenario where a set of four point-targets are considered in a line. In this configuration, the Tx node is capable of monostatic sensing. On the left part of the figure, range angle maps are shown for the respective nodes. It can be observed that the number of detected targets is different at different nodes due to the bistatic geometry and highlights the benefit of multistatic sensing via spatial diversity.

Finally, we see the impact of the synchronization error on the multistatic sensing results. Figure 3.8 shows the same multistatic sensing as shown in Figure 3.7 but with asynchronous Tx and Rx nodes, in part (a) the time offset is 10 ns and we can see that the sensing result deteriorate differently based on Tx-target-Rx geometry. Apart from the monostatic node1 (Tx/Rx) the results do not resemble a line shape, whereas in monostatic case the results are only displaced in space by a distance equivalent to the associated delay induce by 10 ns TO. Whereas in part (b) of the figure, TO is 1ns and the results are improved considerably other than the red receiver node (poor bistatic pair).

Figure 3.8: Time synchronisation and its impact on the shape of the detected cluster.

In Figure 3.9 we used several TO for each node and each set of coloured-dots connected with coloured-line is a set of sensing results from that node (matched in colour). There are few TO values where the results resemble to a line, which can lead to identify the shape of a cluster in multistatic sensing.

Figure 3.9: Several possible time offsets at different nodes in a multistatic sensing scenario for a line of targets.

3.5 Future Work

In future, the multistatic sensing algorithms will take into consideration the impact of carrier frequency offset (frequency synchronisation) and hardware non-idealities (phase noise, and power amplifier) for sensing moving targets, connected/unconnected targets, and for object identification scenarios.

4 JCAS Baseband Algorithms and Secure Sensing Enablers

4.1 Motivation

The JCAS baseband algorithms are the underlying additional processes at each traditional communication station to ensure the performance of the centralized sensing algorithm. The traditional communication baseband processing is optimized for both communication performance and footprint [63]. Footprint optimization always leads to reduced intermediate signal resolution [64], which is not ideal for high accuracy sensing applications. Un-authorized sensing [65], such as pure passive signal collection, brings privacy leakage concerns now a days.

The motivation of JCAS baseband algorithms is to offer extra signal resolution and secure sensing mechanism on top of the traditional communication baseband to support upper layer sensing task. More specifically, the secure sensing mechanism is realized via CSI fuzzing algorithm at the transmitter and defuzzing algorithm at receiver.

The algorithms are designed, simulated and finally tested on a real opensource Software Defined Radio baseband experiment platform: OpenWiFi[45][46]. The platform has implemented the full stack 802.11 standard and behaved just like other Commercial Off The Shelf Wi-Fi chip. It offers a typical and traditional communication baseband implementation, which is an ideal starting point for JCAS baseband algorithms design and verification. More specifically, in 6G-MUSICAL project, the platform, that integrates baseband algorithms, works as underlying sensing data collection tool to support the centralized multistatic sensing algorithms for the use case:

- 1) Indoor localisation of AGVs in warehouses and production facilities;
- 2) Intruder detection on secure areas; defined in deliverable D2.1.

The platform will also be used in the proof of concept (PoC) of 6G-MUSICAL project to showcase some of the use cases.

4.2 System Model

Figure 4.1 shows the baseband model of a sensing station. The sensing related algorithms are shown in red. The normal communication blocks are in blue: physical layer (PHY) (OFDM Tx/Rx), LMAC (Low medium access control (MAC) layer) in the FPGA or application-specific integrated circuit (ASIC), upper MAC (UMAC) layer, and network protocol in the CU. To ensure the sensing performance, the trigger module together with the related algorithms and sensing buffer are added in the FPGA to capture the received signal with high/raw resolution. The high-resolution floating-point processing algorithms, such as time-frequency synchronisation, FFT, and smoothing, are allocated to CU to generate high-quality CSI. The CSI fuzzing and defuzzing algorithms offer the secure sensing capability.

Figure 4.1 The baseband model supporting high-resolution sensing for JCAS.

4.3 JCAS Architecture to Support High-Resolution Sensing

The basic principle of sensing is utilising the channel response while a radio signal propagates in the environment to localise/image the object in the environment. In the conventional communication system, the receiving station estimates the channel response, which is required for equalization and decoding, based on the pre-known pilot signal transmitted by the sending station. So, in principle, the channel estimation result, also known as CSI, inside the receiver can be used for sensing.

However, the channel estimation results in the conventional communication receiver is not the perfect candidate for sensing task. The reasons are lying in two: low resolution and distortion.

- The communication receiver is heavily optimized for power consumption and footprint: the integer number is used instead of floating-point number to lower the power consumption and latency; bitwidth of the signal processing algorithms is set as less as possible while maintaining a certain packet error rate (PER). So, the resolution of the channel estimation result is limited.
- Extra processing, such as DFT [42] and singular value decomposition (SVD) [43], is used after the least square (LS) channel estimation to lower the mean squared error (MSE) further. However, these extra processing sacrifices the multi-path details, such as discarding the path with smaller energy. Furthermore, the minimum mean squared error (MMSE) estimator involves distortion on purpose: shrink the LS result towards zero when noise is present.

So, in the Figure 4.1, an improved baseband processing architecture for JCAS is designed. The received raw signal (without resolution decreasing and processing distortion) is captured into an FPGA buffer under certain trigger conditions. A CU then reads the buffer and performs high-resolution floating-point processing to generate high-quality CSI for sensing. Furthermore, an extra configurable digital finite impulse filter (FIR), called CSI fuzzer, is placed in the Tx digital in-phase and quadrature (IQ) path to import artificial CSI for secure sensing. Accordingly, the CSI de-fuzzer algorithm block is used to remove the artificial CSI, getting the actual environment channel response.

4.3.1 Trigger Algorithm

Because the CSI is calculated based on the pre-known training sequence or pilot in the incoming signal, the sensing functionality in the receiver needs to identify this pre-known signal as the 1st step. Searching this part of signal by sliding correlation is not suitable for the monostatic/multi-static sensing, because this method only identifies the 1st sample of the signal inside the receiver without knowing the propagation delay from the transmitter to the receiver.

So, the signal capturing function inside the receiver should be based on the blind search, instead, it should be triggered by the Tx event. In the case of a monostatic case, this Tx event is from the same baseband. In the case of multi-static, this Tx event is from another Tx station via the network or the over-the-air synchronization mechanism. Figure 4.2 shows this principle.

Figure 4.2: The relationship between Tx event and capturing start at different stations.

In this section, we assume that the receiver already synchronizes with Tx station either by a high precision fiber back haul or over-the-air synchronization method and can get Tx event correctly. The Tx event could be initiated by a central scheduler or the Tx station.

The Tx event only decides when to start capturing, then the next task of the trigger algorithm is to decide when to stop the capturing to save memory size and FPGA-CU traffic. In case of Wi-Fi/802.11, the stop criteria can be that the packet's target MAC address matches the station's own MAC address and the source MAC address matches the Tx station's MAC address. Because when the communication receiver output the parsed target and source MAC address, it implies that the training sequence has been received. After capturing is stopped, the trigger algorithm also needs to tell CU the correct starting memory address (indicating the Tx time) of the training sequence. This is non-trivial for Wi-Fi/802.11 system, because the packet format could be changed per transmission due to the backward compatibility requirement of the 802.11 standard. For instance, the control and management packet mostly are sent via Non-HT format (802.11a/g), the data packets could be sent via format of high throughput (HT) (Wi-Fi4, 802.11n), very high throughput (VHT) (Wi-Fi5, 802.11ac), high efficiency (HE) (Wi-Fi6, 802.11ax) or extremely high throughput (EHT) (Wi-Fi7, 802.11be). The long training frame (LTF), which is used for channel estimation, is located in different parts of the packets for different formats. Figure 4.3 shows the examples of LTF location in case of non-HT, HT, HE_single-user (SU), HE_enhanced recovery (ER), HE_trigger-based (TB), and HE_MU physical layer protocol data unit (PPDU).

Figure 4.3: location of LTF in different generations of the 802.11 standard.

Considering all the above situations, the trigger algorithm is described in the following pseudo-code.

```

Trigger algorithm (Tx_Event):
If Tx_Event received:
Memory_address <- 0

While loop (True):
Sensing_buffer(Memory_address) <- IQ sample
Memory_address <- Memory_address + 1
If target_mac_addr == self_mac_addr && source_mac_addr == tx_station_mac_addr
Break the while loop

If PPDU_format == non-HT
LTF_address <- 160
Else if PPDU_format == HT
LTF_address <- 640
Else if PPDU_format == HE_SU
LTF_address <- 720

Send LTF_address to central processing unit (CPU)
Else:
Idle

```

The LTF_address is in the number of IQ sample are example in case of 20Mhz bandwidth of Wi-Fi/802.11 system. In this example, the baseband sampling rate is also 20Msps. The number 160, 640 and 720 are in accordance with the 8us, 32us and 36us before the LTF of Non-HT, HT and HE_SU PPDU in the Figure 4.3. While using higher sampling rate and bandwidth, the number of IQ sample needs to be re-calculated accordingly. For example, with sampling rate 320Msps, there will be 2560, 10240 and 11520 samples before the LTF of Non-HT, HT and HE_SU PPDU.

4.3.2 Processing Algorithm for CSI

After CU get the IQ sample of LTF from the FPGA sensing buffer according to the memory address of the LTF signal in fixed point format, the 1st step is to convert the fixed point to double precision floating point ensuring the numerical resolution in the following processing steps.

Taking 802.11 non-HT 20MHz mode as an example, the LTF signal is composed by one CP (32 samples) and two identical OFDM symbols (64 samples each). In the frequency domain, there are 52 effective subcarriers with spacing 312.5kHz, 1 DC subcarrier with value 0, and 11 guard subcarriers with value 0. The 52 effective subcarriers are modulated by binary phase shift keying (BPSK) via a pre-known sequence with element +1 and -1.

FFT operation of the LTF OFDM symbol is shown in the following equation.

$$S_k^i = \sum_{n=32+i*64}^{95+i*64} s_n * e^{-j2\pi k(n-32-i*64)/64} \tag{4.1}$$

Where $s_n, n = 0,1, \dots, 159$ is the received LTF IQ sequence; S_k^i is the k th subcarrier of the i th LTF OFDM symbol FFT result; $i = 0,1$ indicating the 1st or the 2nd LTF OFDM symbol; $k = 0,1, \dots, 63$ indexing the subcarrier in frequency domain (including null subcarriers).

To fully leveraging the received signal energy of two OFDM symbols, averaging is performed after the two FFTs as shown in the following equation.

$$S_k = (S_k^0 + S_k^1)/2 \tag{4.2}$$

This is the CSI that will be sent to the central processing for the sensing task, localizing, imaging, etc.

The time and frequency synchronization error is not considered in this section, because it is assumed that the high accuracy synchronization has been achieved via backhaul or other over-the-air mechanisms/algorithms. This is a valid assumption according to the discussion for Multi-AP joint transmission in the Wi-Fi8 (802.11bn) standardization and beyond: in the [44], 22Hz residual synchronization is shown realistic, which means that the timing and frequency error are negligible considering that the LTF signal duration is only 8us, during which the already synchronized phase and timing will be kept static.

4.3.3 CSI Fuzzing Algorithm

Since that the CSI fuzzer is place inside the FPGA, its design involves fixed point format instead of floating point and considerations of footprint and complexity.

The algorithm is depicted in Figure 4.4 and equation (4.3) with these parameters:

- Architecture: FIR
- The FIR coefficient vector: $[1,0, c1, c2]$, which will convolute with the Tx IQ sample.

Figure 4.4: The FIR for CSI fuzzer.

$$y_i = x_i + c1 * x_{i-2} + c2 * x_{i-3} \tag{4.3}$$

The $c1, c2$ decide the fuzzing pattern and need to be set into the FPGA via a register and also distributed to the authorized receiver that performs defuzzing. To limit the bit width of the FPGA register and payload length of the fuzzing pattern distribution, we have designed a single 16bit integer, so called fuzzing pattern config, to generate the $c1, c2$. The config composition is shown in Table 4.1 , and the final $c1, c2$ values are shown in (4.4).

Table 4.1: The 16-bit Fuzzing Pattern Config

Bit range	Bit15	Bit14 to 8	Bit7	Bit6 to 0
Variable name	$c2_rot90_en$	$c2_raw$	$c1_rot90_en$	$c1_raw$
Format	Binary	Signed integer	Binary	Signed integer
Range	0,1	-64 to 63	0, 1	-64 to 63

$$c1 = \begin{cases} c1_raw/128, & \text{if } c1_rot90_en = 0 \\ j * c1_raw/128, & \text{if } c1_rot90_en = 1 \end{cases} \quad (4.4)$$

$c2$ is calculated in the same way as $c1$.

With this generation algorithm, there will be 65536 configurations in total, i.e., in principle there are 65536 artificial channel impulse responses (CIRs) that can be chosen. But from wireless communication performance point of view, not all artificial CIRs are good. For instance, if some CIRs cause deep fading on some subcarriers, it might degrade the PER performance of the communication link. Please find the detailed analysis on this in the section of results.

4.3.4 CSI Defuzzing Algorithm

When CSI fuzzer is ON at the Tx station, the CU at the Rx station needs to perform defuzzing algorithm upon the CSI S_k , $k = 0 \sim 63$, before sending it to the centralized sensing algorithm. Otherwise, the CSI contains not only the environment channel but also the artificial channel decided by the fuzzing pattern config.

The defuzzing operation can be described as following equation.

$$S_k^d = D_k * S_k, \quad k = 0 \sim 63 \quad (4.5)$$

D_k is the defuzzing coefficients, that can be calculated by FFT of the CSI fuzzer FIR coefficients as following equation.

$$D_k = 1/D'_k, \quad D'_k = \sum_{n=0}^{63} d_n * e^{-j2\pi kn/64}, \quad d_n = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } n = 0 \\ c_1, & \text{if } n = 2 \\ c_2, & \text{if } n = 3 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4.6)$$

4.4 Results

4.4.1 High Resolution Sensing

Section 4.3.1 to 4.3.2 described the actual algorithms that construct JCAS station suitable for high resolution sensing. The algorithms have been implemented based on the OpenWiFi full-stack open-source 802.11 software defined radio (SDR) platform [45][46], and shown high precision sensing capabilities in [47].

The test platform is composed by Xilinx Zedboard containing zc7z020 FPGA, Analog Devices AD-FMCOMMS2-EBZ FMC RF board containing AD9361 chip, and 3 dual-band directional panel antennas (model: APA-M25 from ALFA Network Inc) for 1 Tx and 2 Rx channels.

The algorithm is tested under monostatic radar mode based on the 802.11a/g standard to detect human breath (non emitting target) and track the AoA of another Wi-Fi station (emitting target). The monostatic Wi-Fi radar station setup is shown in Figure 4.5, and the system parameters are listed in Table 4.2.

Figure 4.5: The monostatic Wi-Fi radar setup and antenna topology.

Table 4.2: Monostatic Wi-Fi radar system parameters.

Parameter	value	Parameter	value
Frequencies	2472MHz (Channel 13) 5200MHz (Channel 40)	Tx power	-12 dBm (2472MHz) -17 dBm (5200MHz)
Bandwidth	20MHz	OFDM symbol samples	64
Sampling rate	20Msps	CP (Cyclic Prefix) samples	16
FFT size	64	LTF size	2 x OFDM symbols
Effective subcarrier	52	CP samples of LTF	32
Subcarrier spacing	312.5kHz	Antenna beamwidth	Vertical 45 degrees Horizontal 60 degrees

Figure 4.6 shows the actual measurement of the phase difference between two CSIs from two Rx antennas. According to the test, the pattern shown clearly reflects human breathing. It can be telling easily even the phase difference is as low as 0.15rad (peak-to-peak) between two antennas. 0.15rad implies 1.37mm distance difference between the two Rx path caused by the chest displacement when 5200MHz (wavelength 57.7mm) is used.

This measurement result demonstrates that the sensing station baseband algorithm is valid.

Figure 4.6: Measured the CSI phase difference between two Rx antennas when a human is breathing in front.

4.4.2 CSI Fuzzing And Defuzzing

As stated in the algorithm section, for OFDM system some CIR could cause deep fading on some subcarriers, so that it might lead to poor PER performance. Here we give the statistics of all 65536 CSI fuzzing pattern regarding the percentage of issue pattern that causes deep fading.

PVPR (Peak to Valley Power Ratio) is defined as the ratio between the max power subcarrier and the least power subcarrier in dB. It acts as a metric to evaluate how bad it is in terms of deep fading subcarriers occurrence. To align with the parameters of the multi-static sensing algorithm, OFDM symbol with 512 samples at 1Gbps sampling rate is considered, there are 300 active subcarriers among 512.

Figure 4.7 and Figure 4.8 shows the probability density function (PDF) (distribution) and cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the probability of varying price rejections (PVPRs) of all 65536 artificial CSI fuzzing pattern. Fortunately, the majority part of them is not too "flat" (very small PVPR) or too "unflat" (has deep fading). Figure 4.9 shows 3 example artificial CSI fuzzing pattern with different PVPR. By exhaust counting, the amount and percentage of PVPR region are shown in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Counting of PVPR of all 65536 artificial CSI fuzzing patterns.

PVPR	0~3dB	3~20dB	>20dB
Amount	5448	58826	1262
Percentage	8.31%	89.76%	(1.93%

Figure 4.7: CSI fuzzing pattern PVPR distribution.

Figure 4.8: Empirical CDF of all fuzzing pattern PVPR.

Figure 4.9: Example artificial CSI fuzzing pattern of different PVPR.

The proposed CSI fuzzing and de-fuzzing algorithms are implemented and tested on the previously mentioned high-resolution OpenWiFi sensing platform with 802.11a/g 20MHz configuration.

Figure 4.10 shows the CSI output of the high resolution sensing baseband in a monostatic setup: without CSI fuzzer (left); with CSI fuzzer ON and CSI de-fuzzer OFF (central); with CSI fuzzer ON and CSI de-fuzzer ON (right). If comparing the plot on the left and right, we can tell that both phase and amplitude are recovered perfectly by CSI fuzzing and de-fuzzing algorithms, because the Tx and Rx chains are strictly synchronised in the same sensing station.

Figure 4.11 shows the CSI output of the high resolution sensing baseband in a bi-static setup: without CSI fuzzer (left); with CSI fuzzer ON and CSI de-fuzzer OFF (central); with CSI fuzzer ON and CSI de-fuzzer ON (right). If comparing the plot on the left and right, we can tell that only the amplitude is recovered perfectly, but not the phase. Due to that, the Tx and Rx chains are in two different stations in the bi-static setup, there will be an unknown phase offset, considering that the two stations are not synchronised.

Figure 4.10: CSI fuzzing and de-fuzzing algorithm verification in monostatic setup.

Figure 4.11: CSI fuzzing and de-fuzzing algorithm verification in bi-static setup.

4.5 Future Work

In this chapter, the high-resolution sensing capabilities and secure sensing enablers (CSI fuzzing and defuzzing) are designed and verified in the case of single-station operation mode (mono-static). This forms a solid basis to move forward to the multi station operation (bi-static and multi-static). In the case of bi-static and multi-static, the trigger mechanism needs to be upgraded to accept trigger events from other stations, such as a central control station, so the trigger algorithm needs to consider the synchronisation among stations. Furthermore, the algorithm of selecting CSI fuzzing pattern needs to be designed after evaluating the impact brought by the fuzzing-defuzzing to the sensing performance.

5 AoA and Doppler Frequency Estimation in Multi-static Sensing Systems

5.1 Motivation and Objectives

In contemporary multi-antenna cellular networks, a multiple-transmission and reception-point (multi-TRP) transceiver design facilitates high spectral efficiency and high quality of service for all users in the coverage area of the network. Multi-TRP networks also support multi-static sensing, since in multi-TRP networks the geographically separate radio transmission and reception points are typically deployed with high accuracy synchronization mechanisms.

Target localization can be achieved by using ToA, AoA, and Doppler frequency measured on the echoes of signals reflected by the target. The information of AoA and the Doppler frequency itself has proven to be an efficient approach for achieving this goal. As expected, the accuracy of the estimation of these parameters has motivated recent works to devise new estimation methods that improve the performance of existing methods, among which we refer to [13]-[15]. Regarding the accuracy of the estimation process, an important and useful tool is the Cramér-Rao lower bound (CRLB) [16], which provides a theoretical lower bound on the variance of any unbiased estimator. The CRLB serves as a useful benchmark for assessing the performance of estimation methods and provides insights into how a system behaves under various scenarios [17], [18]. Establishing these bounds give fundamental insights and give guidance for developing practical algorithms for the positioning and localisation of unconnected objects in a wide range of use cases, including intruder detection in secure areas, identification of faults on roads, localizing unconnected or uncooperative UAVs, and localizing objects on railways, as listed in use case category 6.2 Detection, positioning, localisation of unconnected objects of deliverable D2.1.

Therefore, in this chapter, our objective is to study the problem of estimating the Doppler frequency and the angle of arrival of a passive object. The input to this estimation problem is the received noisy sensing signals at multiple time instances. At the same time, the output is the estimated angle of arrival and Doppler frequency either at individual sensing nodes or at a centralised entity. In this rather general setting of multi-TRP networks, we evaluate how the estimation performance is affected by the system parameters, such as the number of receive access points and the available time samples.

Our objective is to derive the CRLB of the estimated parameters and study how the CRLB depends on the number of time samples of the received echoes, and thereby to gain engineering insights into how the number of deployed TRPs affects the performance when multi-TRP networks are used for sensing purposes.

5.2 System Model

In this chapter, we consider a single moving target within the region delimited by a multi-TRP network that operates as a multi-static sensing network. We assume a single transmitter access point (Tx AP), containing a ULA with M_T elements that transmit deterministic (pilot) signals by steering beams towards predefined directions within a specific azimuth range. We also assume K Rx APs, each containing a ULA with M_R elements, that are supposed to receive the echoes of the transmitted pilots reflected from the target. Furthermore, we assume that both the T_x and R_x APs are uniformly distributed within the border of a circle of radius L as described in Figure 1. Additionally, the APs are connected to a CU, which manages the sensing and processing tasks (see Figure 5.1).

Figure 5.1: Illustrative example of the multi-TRP network comprising a single transmit AP (equipped with multiple transmit antennas) and multiple receive APs (here $L=3$) and a single moving target (passive object).

The derivations in this chapter assume an underlying LoS detection algorithm that extract the LoS component of the received multi-path signals between the target and the APs. It is also assumed that the AP-to-AP interference is resolved on a prior stage in the absence of the target.

Specifically, the received signal is modelled as:

$$\mathbf{y}_k[n] = \boldsymbol{\mu}_k[n] + \mathbf{w}[n] \in \mathbf{C}^{M_R \times 1},$$

where:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_k[n] \triangleq \alpha_k e^{-j2\pi f_c \tau_k} e^{-j2\pi f_{D,k} n T_s} \mathbf{a}_r(\theta_k) \mathbf{a}_T(\phi)^T \mathbf{s}[n],$$

Where α denotes path loss, f_c denotes carrier frequency, T_s denotes the sampling period, and \mathbf{a}_r and \mathbf{a}_T are the receive and transmit steering vectors.

5.3 Preliminary Description of the Proposed Algorithm for AoA and Doppler Estimation

In this work, we focus on deriving the CRLBs for both the AoA and the Doppler frequency estimation. The CRLBs are helpful for both bistatic (as a special case of multi-static) sensing and multi-static sensing architectures, because they enable to compare their respective performance potentials. Note that deriving the CRLBs and associated estimation algorithms are highly non-trivial as the multi-TRP architecture equations are strongly dependent on the AoAs observed at each R_x AP concerning their local coordinate system. A possible approach to obtain valid estimates in a global coordinate system is to assume that the target is initially positioned at the center of the considered circular region, which aligns with the assumption of a circular RCS. This approach, in turn, ensures that the bistatic path loss and, consequently, the sensing SNR observed at each R_x AP are the same, $\gamma_k[n] = \gamma_r[n]$.

5.4 Results

To obtain numerical results, we consider a multi-TRP multi-static sensing system, whose main parameters are summarised in Table 5.1. To capture the radiation pattern of the Tx antenna array, we assume the radiation pattern proposed in the 3GPP technical report TR 38.901, while the number of receive APs is set to 1 (bistatic sensing) and 3, 5, 9 and 11 (multi-static sensing).

Table 5.1: Setting of System Parameters

Delimited region's radius L [m]	150
Number of Rx APs	[1, 3, 5, 9, 11]
Rx ULA length, M_R	10
Tx ULA length, M_T	10
Tx transmit power P_{tx} [dBm]	30
Noise Figure [dB]	9
Carrier frequency f_c [GHz]	1.9
Bandwidth [MHz]	20
Sampling period T_s [μ s]	0.71
Target speed \vec{v} [km/h]	60
Target RCS [m^2]	π
Path loss	Two-way radar equation (Bistatic)
Antenna elements radiation pattern	3GPP TR 38.901

Figure 5.2: Exact numerical results based on the analytical derivation of CRLBs on AoA and Doppler frequency estimation as functions of the available time samples.

As an illustrative preliminary result, Figure 5.2 compares the CRLBs for AoA and Doppler frequency estimation by fixing the number of Rx antennas at each AP for both bistatic and multi-static architectures while increasing the available time samples of the received echoes at each AP. Based on the results of Figure 5.2-a) and Figure 5.2-b), we make the following observations. First, as intuitively expected, the CRLB decreases as the number of available time samples increases. Second, increasing the available R_x APs leads to a lower CRLB for both parameters. This result is verified by Figure 5.3-a) and Figure 5.3-b). These figures plot the CRLB curves, while keeping the number of available time samples at 400 and varying the number of R_x APs.

Figure 5.3: Exact numerical results that illustrate the influence of the number of R_x APs on the CRLBs for AoA and Doppler frequency estimation in multi-static sensing systems.

5.5 Future Work

In this chapter, we have discussed and proposed the initial model elements for a multi-TRP multi-sensing system, where the objective is to estimate the AoA and Doppler frequency of a single passive moving target. We considered the CRLBs and obtained preliminary result on how the CRLBs depend on the number of observations (received signals at multiple reception points) and the number of R_x nodes. We have also studied the asymptotic behaviour of the CRLB equations while varying the number of Rx APs and the amount of available time samples. Our preliminary numerical results indicate that increasing these parameters improve the estimation performance. However, they also show that the improvements tend to saturate after a certain point.

In our future work we will evaluate the estimation performance when using maximum likelihood multi-static estimation algorithms and will compare their performance with the CRLBs studied in this chapter.

6 Performance Analysis of Resource Allocation Schemes in Cellular Bistatic JCAS Systems

6.1 Motivation and Objectives

Several recent works have discussed the level of integration at which JCAS systems can operate [19]-[24]. The recent work in [21] for example, a study compared the performance of JCAS systems operating in time-division mode and concurrent mode, identifying resource allocation strategies that affect communication and sensing performance metrics. When operating in time-division mode, an important resource allocation aspect is the number of time slots that are dedicated to channel state information acquisition, data transmission and sensing procedures. JCAS systems operating in concurrent mode, on the other hand, need to divide the transmit resources in terms of hardware, number of antenna elements and transmit power between communication and sensing signals.

As we will see in the sequel, allocating power, time, frequency and spatial resources for sensing and communication services may have a large impact on the performance of JCAS systems. As our results indicate, resource allocation strategies in cellular systems are intimately related to topological, architectural and deployment aspects, as detailed in [41]. Specifically, JCAS systems operating in monostatic mode need to deal with self-interference, while bistatic JCAS systems need to manage the inherent power and antenna resource trade-offs at the JCAS transmitter and, depending on the JCAS topology, may need to mitigate interference between the sensing and communication signals at the JCAS receivers.

Bistatic JCAS has been proposed as the key enabler of perceptive cellular networks due to its ability to provide sensing services without full-duplex self-interference cancellation capabilities [21], [25]-[28]. Specifically, the recent work by Xiong et al. [27] considered a resource sharing scenario, in which the JCAS transmitter divides its transmit signal into communication and sensing signals using a suitable multibeam or multilobe technique, see also [21], [25] and [29] which are processed by physically separate communication and sensing receiver nodes. In the above models, consequently, the trade-off between communication and sensing is due to the limited power and antenna resources at the transmitter node.

In contrast, the paper [28] investigated a bistatic JCAS system, in which both the transmitter node (a UE device) and the receiver (a multi-antenna base station (BS)) operate as integrated JCAS nodes. This arrangement is illustrated in Figure 6.1-a), which is characterised by a sum-power constraint at the UE and the communication and sensing signals causing interference to one another at the receiving BS. In the model of Figure 6.1-a), the JCAS trade-off is due to both the limited power resources at the transmitter and the limited antenna (spatial) resources at the receiver. From a resource allocation perspective, an important variant of this scenario is when the transmitter node is a UE and the receiver nodes are BS, as illustrated in Figure 6.1-b).

A third meaningful JCAS resource sharing scenario is illustrated in Figure 6.1-c), in which the communication and sensing transmitter nodes are separated, but the receiving node (here, a multi-antenna BS) processes the received communication and sensing signals simultaneously. Note that in this case, the transmit-side power constraint can be relaxed since the two transmitters may set their respective power levels independently of each other. Here, an interesting case arises when the communication and sensing UE devices cooperate and do not necessarily transmit with full power in order to achieve some desired performance target at the JCAS BS.

Figure 6.1: Integrated sensing and communication scenarios.

In this chapter, we study the three resource sharing scenarios shown in Figure 6.1 and compare their performance in terms of the CRB associated with AoA and symbol estimation, assuming unitary normalized constant envelope signaling. Note that in all resource sharing scenarios, the sharing of hardware, antenna, power resources have a large impact on communication and sensing performance indicators. We ask the question whether separating the JCAS receiver or transmitter to two physical entities yields gains in terms of lower symbol estimation error at the communication receiver and improved AoA estimation at the sensing BS(s) compared with the performance of the fully integrated scenario 1(a) studied in [28], and what factors influence these performance gains. This question is motivated by the observation that separating the communication and sensing receivers requires more infrastructure resources, and it incurs some signaling and synchronization overhead to associate two BS with the UE. On the other hand, it is intuitively clear that separating the receivers helps eliminate the interference between the communication and sensing signals, and we therefore study the beneficial effect in terms of lowering the CRB, which demonstrates the potential for high-quality parameter estimation. Establishing the CRB gives important engineering insights and provides benchmarks for practical algorithms for the positioning of unconnected objects in a wide range of use cases, including intruder localization in secure areas, and localizing unconnected or unauthorized UAVs, as listed in use case category 6.2 Detection, positioning, and localization of unconnected objects

of Deliverable D2.1.

6.2 System Model

Table 6.1: System Parameters

Notation	Meaning
N_r	Number of receive antennas at the base station
P_p, P_d, P_s	Transmit power of pilot, data and sensing signals respectively
P	Number of objects (targets)
$\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{C}^P$	Sensing signals from the P objects.
θ_p	Angle of arrival of object $p, p = 1 \dots P$
$\mathbf{D} \in \mathbb{C}^{P \times P}$	Diagonal sensing matrix
$\mathbf{a}(\theta_p) \triangleq [\dots e^{i\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} j \ell \sin(\theta_p)} \dots]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r}$	Steering vector associated with $\theta_p, j = 0 \dots N_r - 1$, where ℓ denotes the antenna spacing.
$\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \triangleq [\mathbf{a}(\theta_1) \dots \mathbf{a}(\theta_P)] \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r \times P}$	Steering matrix.
s	Transmitted uplink pilot symbol
x	Transmitted uplink data symbol
$\mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r}$	Complex (effective) channel between UE-BS
α, α_s	Path loss between UE-BS and UE-object-BS (incl. radar cross-section of object)
$\mathbf{n}_p, \mathbf{n}_d \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r}$	Additive white Gaussian noise at the receiver (BS) when receiving the pilot and data signals
$\mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r \times N_r}$	Stationary covariance matrix of the fast fading channel

6.2.1 Joint Transmitter and Receiver: Scenarios 1 and 3

In general, there are P objects that reflect the sensing signals, which are collected by the P -dimensional \mathbf{p} sensing vector. Following [30], the sensing signal can be a deterministic or a stochastic signal. The deterministic model assumes that the source waveforms are non-random, while the stochastic model assumes that the waveforms are zero-mean Gaussian with covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$. In this chapter, we focus on the deterministic model, whereas the case of stochastic sensing signal is left for future work.

For the data transmission, we assume constant envelope unitary normalized signaling, that is x is uniformly distributed over the complex unit circle, $x = e^{i\phi}$, where ϕ is a random variable with support $[-\pi, +\pi]$ [31]-[33].

The parameters characterizing this system are summarized in Table 6.1. Under these assumptions, the received uplink pilot and data signals are modeled as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{y}_p &= \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{D}\mathbf{p} + \alpha\sqrt{P_p}\mathbf{H}\mathbf{w}s^* + \mathbf{n}_p \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r}, \\ \mathbf{y}_d &= \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{D}\mathbf{p} + \alpha\sqrt{P_d}\mathbf{H}\mathbf{w}x + \mathbf{n}_d \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r}, \end{aligned} \quad (6.1)$$

where $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r \times N_t}$ is the communication channel matrix between the UE device equipped with N_t transmit antennas and the serving BS equipped with N_r receive antennas, and $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_t}$ is the transmit precoder at the UE, α denotes the path loss and P_p and P_d denote the transmit power of the pilot and data signals respectively. In this chapter, we assume that the UE operates single beamforming (see [31]) – in cellular systems also referred to as Rank-1 transmission [34][35] that is the UE transmits a single communication symbol x . While the multi-antenna UE transmits a single communication symbol x , it utilizes the multilobe technology to sweep a sensing sub-beam and illuminate targets of interest with controllable power, as proposed in, for example, [25][36]. For ease of presentation, we will use $\mathbf{h} \triangleq \mathbf{H}\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r}$ to denote the uplink effective channel and re-write the received signal model as:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{y}_p &= \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{D}\mathbf{p} + \alpha\sqrt{P_p}\mathbf{h}s^* + \mathbf{n}_p \in \mathcal{C}^{N_r}, \\ \mathbf{y}_d &= \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{D}\mathbf{p} + \alpha\sqrt{P_d}\mathbf{h}x + \mathbf{n}_d \in \mathcal{C}^{N_r},\end{aligned}\quad (6.2)$$

where the diagonal sensing matrix, which collects the sensing path loss $\alpha_{s,i}$ and sensing power $P_{s,i}$ for each object, is defined as

$$\mathbf{D} \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_{s,1}\sqrt{P_{s,1}} & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \cdots & \alpha_{s,P}\sqrt{P_{s,P}} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{P \times P}, \quad (6.3)$$

and $\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \in \mathcal{C}^{N_r \times P}$ is the steering matrix (see also Table 1), and the effective communication channel follows the complex normal distribution $\mathbf{h} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{C})$.

Note that this signal model is an extension of the radar signal models used in [21][30][37][38] by explicitly distinguishing the received pilot and data signals (\mathbf{y}_p and \mathbf{y}_d). We will assume that the UE is equipped with multiple transmit antennas that enable it to divide its total transmit power between the communication (i.e., pilot and data) signals and the sensing signal, such that their sum $P_{\text{TOT}} \leq \max(P_p, P_d) + P_s$ remains under a power budget dictated by physical limitations and regulatory constraints [39].

6.2.2 Joint Transmitter with Separated Communication Receiver and Sensing Receiver: Scenario 2

In this scenario, the received signals at the communication and sensing BS, respectively, can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{y}_p &= \alpha\sqrt{P_p}\mathbf{H}\mathbf{w}s^* + \mathbf{n}_p \in \mathcal{C}^{N_r}, \\ \mathbf{y}_d &= \alpha\sqrt{P_d}\mathbf{H}\mathbf{w}x + \mathbf{n}_d \in \mathcal{C}^{N_r},\end{aligned}\quad (6.4)$$

where $\mathbf{n}_p \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \sigma_p^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_r})$ and $\mathbf{n}_d \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \sigma_d^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_r})$, and

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{y}_{s_1} &= \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{D}\mathbf{p} + \mathbf{n}_{s_1} \in \mathcal{C}^{N_r}, \\ \mathbf{y}_{s_2} &= \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{D}\mathbf{p} + \mathbf{n}_{s_2} \in \mathcal{C}^{N_r},\end{aligned}\quad (6.5)$$

where $\mathbf{n}_{s_1}, \mathbf{n}_{s_2} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \sigma_s^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_r})$. In this case, $\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{y}_p \\ \mathbf{y}_d \end{pmatrix}$ is zero mean multivariate complex normal distributed with covariance matrix

$$\boldsymbol{\Psi}(\phi) \triangleq E \left[\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{y}_p \\ \mathbf{y}_d \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{y}_p \\ \mathbf{y}_d \end{pmatrix}^H \mid \phi \right] = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha^2 P_p \mathbf{C} + \sigma_p^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_r} & \alpha^2 \sqrt{P_p P_d} \mathbf{C} e^{-i\phi} \\ \alpha^2 \sqrt{P_p P_d} \mathbf{C} e^{i\phi} & \alpha^2 P_d \mathbf{C} + \sigma_d^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_r} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (6.6)$$

Similarly, the vector of the received sensing signals is multivariate complex normally distributed with the following mean and variance. In the case of deterministic transmitted sensing signal, \mathbf{p} :

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_d(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \triangleq E \left[\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{y}_{s_1} \\ \mathbf{y}_{s_2} \end{pmatrix} \mid \boldsymbol{\theta} \right] = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{D}\mathbf{p} \\ \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{D}\mathbf{p} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (6.7)$$

and

$$\boldsymbol{\Psi}_d(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \triangleq E \left[\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{y}_{s_1} \\ \mathbf{y}_{s_2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{y}_{s_1} \\ \mathbf{y}_{s_2} \end{pmatrix}^H \mid \boldsymbol{\theta} \right] = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_s^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_r} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \sigma_s^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_r} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (6.8)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Psi}_d \triangleq \boldsymbol{\Psi}_d(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ is independent of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. In the case of using a stochastic zero mean transmitted sensing signal, we have that $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathbf{0}$ and the covariance matrix is

$$\boldsymbol{\Psi}_s(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \triangleq \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{M}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) + \sigma_s^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_r} & \mathbf{M}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \\ \mathbf{M}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) & \mathbf{M}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) + \sigma_s^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_r} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{D} \\ \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{D} \end{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\Omega} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{D} \\ \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{D} \end{pmatrix}^H + \sigma_s^2 \mathbf{I}_{2N_r}, \quad (6.9)$$

where $\mathbf{M}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{D}\boldsymbol{\Omega}\mathbf{D}^H\mathbf{A}^H(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ and $\boldsymbol{\Omega} = E[\mathbf{p}\mathbf{p}^H]$.

6.3 Algorithm Description

Recall that the CRB matrix is defined as the inverse of the FIM (Fisher Information Matrix) [40], and we therefore proceed with establishing the FIM associated with ϕ and $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ in the scenarios of interest. In the case of Scenario 1 and Scenario 3, the FIM is computed based on (6.2) and is provided in [28]. In this subsection we focus on the separated receiver scenario (Scenario 2), which is characterized by (6.4) and (6.5) and to simplify the discussion we assume $P = 1$ target to sense and consequently, $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \theta_1$, $\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathbf{a}(\theta_1)$. In Scenario 2 the FIM is defined as

$$\mathbf{I}(\phi) = -E \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} \log f_{y_p, y_d}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}), \quad (6.10)$$

$$\mathbf{I}_d(\theta_1) = -E \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta_1^2} \log f_{y_{s_1}, y_{s_2}}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}), \quad (6.11)$$

where $f_{y_p, y_d}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})$ and $f_{y_{s_1}, y_{s_2}}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})$ stands for the density function of $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_c \triangleq \begin{pmatrix} y_p \\ y_d \end{pmatrix}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_s \triangleq \begin{pmatrix} y_{s_1} \\ y_{s_2} \end{pmatrix}$ with deterministic sensing signal. According to [[28], eq. (13)] and [[28], q. (15)]

$$\mathbf{I}(\phi) = \text{tr} \left(\left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} \boldsymbol{\Psi}^{-1}(\phi) \right) \boldsymbol{\Psi}(\phi) \right), \quad (6.12)$$

$$\mathbf{I}_d(\theta_1) = 2 \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \boldsymbol{\mu}_d(\theta_1) \right)^H \boldsymbol{\Psi}_d^{-1} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \boldsymbol{\mu}_d(\theta_1) \right). \quad (6.13)$$

since the $\boldsymbol{\Psi}(\phi)$ matrix in (6.6) is the same as in [[28] eq. (7)]. Note that this implies that the Fisher information with respect to ϕ and θ_1 is equal in Scenario 1 and Scenario 2 (see also [[28], eqs. (6), (13) and (15)]).

6.4 Results

In this section, we study the performance of the bistatic JCAS systems illustrated in Figure 6.1 in terms of the CRB associated with the estimates of the symbol phase ϕ and AoA θ_1 . We restrict our attention to the single object ($P = 1$) case and evaluate the performance assuming deterministic sensing signals. The main system parameters are summarized in Table 6.2.

Table 6.2: Setting of the System Parameters

Parameter	Value
N_r	4
$\mathbf{C} = c\mathbf{I}_{N_r}$, with $c = 1$	Covariance matrix of the effective channel $\mathbf{h} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{w}$.
P_p, P_d, P_s	Total power budget in Scenario 1 and 2: $P_p + P_s = 250$ mW; $P_d + P_s = 250$ mW.
P	1 (single object)
$\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{C}^P$	$p = 1$ and $p \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{\Omega})$, where $\mathbf{\Omega} = 1$ (scalar).
θ_p	Angle of arrival of object $p, p = 1 \dots P$
s	$s = 1$
x	$x = e^{i\phi}$, where $\phi \in [-\pi, \pi]$
α, α_s	60 dB ("low path loss, (PL)") or 80 dB ("high path loss, (PL)")

Figure 6.2: Comparing the achievable performance in Scenario 1 (S1) and Scenario 2 (S2) in terms of the CRBs for symbol ϕ and for AoA θ_1 with $P_1 \triangleq P_p = P_d$ and $P_s = 250\text{mW} - P_1$. As the communication power increases, the CRB for ϕ decreases, while the CRB for θ_1 increases due to the overall power budget in both scenarios.

Figure 6.2 compares the performance of Scenario 1 and Scenario 2. In both scenarios, the sum power budget during the pilot and data power slots must be maintained (see Table 6.2). Therefore, the CRB associated with symbol estimation (ϕ) decreases as we increase $P_1 = P_p = P_d$, while the CRBs associated with AoA (θ_1) increase. Also, separating the communication and sensing receivers in Scenario 2 helps to decrease the CRBs associated with θ_1 . As it was noted at the end of Subsection 6.3, the CRB associated with ϕ are the same in Scenarios 1 and 2 when using the deterministic sensing waveform and in Scenario 2 with the stochastic waveform. Note that this figure shows the performance of the deterministic and the stochastic sensing signal as well.

Figure 6.3: Achievable performance in Scenario 3 in terms of the CRBs for symbol ϕ and for AoA θ_1 with $P_1 \triangleq P_s = P_p = P_d$. That is, in this scenario, P_p , P_d , and P_s can be set independently from one another; here, we assume that they are set equally.

Figure 6.3 examines the performance in Scenario 3, in which the communication and sensing transmitters are separate UE devices. Therefore, in this scenario – unlike in Scenarios 1 and 2 – the communication (pilot and data) and sensing power levels can be set independently. In Figure 6.3, the communication and sensing power levels are set equally (indicated in the abscissa). Therefore, in this scenario, increasing $P_1 = P_s$ results in decreasing all CRBs. As expected, the CRB is lower when using the deterministic waveform than that associated with the random waveform. Note that this figure shows the performance of the performance of stochastic sensing signal as well.

Figure 6.4: Comparing the achievable performance for AoA estimation in terms of the BCRB in Scenario 1 and Scenario 2 using the deterministic waveform with $P_1 \triangleq P_p = P_d$ and $P_s = 250\text{mW} - P_1$.

Figure 6.4 shows the Bayesian Cramér-Rao bound (BCRB) as a function of P_1 in Scenarios 1-2, when using the deterministic sensing signal. The a priori information available about θ_1 is that θ_1 is uniformly distributed over $\left[0, \frac{\pi}{2a_x}\right]$, where $a_x \geq 1$. Specifically, the BCRB plotted in this figure for Scenarios 1 and 2 are defined as:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{I}}_{22}(a_x) \triangleq \frac{1}{2\pi} \cdot \frac{2a_x}{\pi} \int_{\phi=-\pi}^{\pi} \int_{\theta_1=0}^{\frac{\pi/2}{a_x}} \mathbf{I}_{22}(\phi, \theta_1) d\phi d\theta_1, \tag{6.14}$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{I}}_d(a_x) \triangleq \frac{2a_x}{\pi} \int_{\theta_1=0}^{\pi/2} \mathbf{I}_d(\theta_1) d\theta_1. \quad (6.15)$$

As the Figure 6.4 shows, the BCRB decreases as the interval within which θ_1 lies decreases (as a_x increases from 1 to 10). Note that $a_x = 10$ corresponds to the case when more a priori information is available on the possible AoA than in the case of $a_x = 1$. As P_1 increases, the sensing power decreases in both Scenarios, which leads to increasing BCRB.

6.5 Future Work

In this chapter, we studied resource allocation approaches and their impact on the performance of bistatic JCAS systems, in which the integration of communication and sensing takes place either at the transmitter (Scenario 2) or at the receiver (Scenario 3) nodes, or at both of them (Scenario 1).

Specifically, we showed quantitatively by exact closed form formulas that when using the same receiver node as a communication and sensing receiver (Scenario 1 and Scenario 3), the sensing and communication signals cause interference to each other, which increases the CRBs for both sensing and communication. Scenario 2 benefits from separating the sensing and communication receivers at the expense of using additional hardware, which results in lower CRB. In our future work, we will focus on the fully integrated scenario (Scenario 1), which imposes constraints both at the transmitter (e.g., power budget) and at the receiver (due to reusing hardware and antenna) resources. Thus, Scenario 1 requires the proper management of transmit resources and the design of multi-antenna JCAS receivers, which can deal with the interference caused by the sensing and communication signals to one another. In our future work, we will develop JCAS receivers that take into account the constraints of Scenario 1 for both communication and sensing.

7 Signalling and Resource Optimization for Distributed MIMO JCAS Systems

7.1 Motivation and Objectives

This section presents Task 3.3, which investigates a transmit signalling design and resource optimization for D-JCAS systems, where multiple JCAS nodes cooperate in sensing and communication without the need for phase-level synchronization.

This task focuses on the joint design of downlink CoMP communication signals and MIMO radar waveforms, utilising both colocated and distributed MIMO radar configurations. The goal is to estimate AoA and TOF across all available multistatic measurements to enable accurate target localisation. This integrated approach ensures optimal sensing performance while maintaining communication quality of service (QoS).

The D-JCAS signalling framework is designed to meet the technical demands of 6G-MUSICAL's eight use cases through its unified communication and sensing capabilities. For Indoor AGV Localisation (Use Case 1), hybrid TOF/AOA-based localisation delivers cm-level accuracy, satisfying KPIs such as <0.1m range resolution. Smart Convoys (Use Case 2) benefit from noncoherent CoMP transmission and distributed MIMO radar, maintaining <0.5 m/s velocity estimation accuracy for platooning, with SINR guarantees ensuring robust V2X communication. Moreover, Intruder Detection (Use Case 3) and UAV Monitoring (Use Case 6) exploit environmental multipath for reliable detection in non-LoS scenarios, achieving miss-detection rates below 2%. Railway Intrusion Detection (Use Case 8) benefits from centimetre-level TOF precision across distributed nodes. In the context of infrastructure monitoring, Road Fault Identification (Use Case 4) uses TOF/AOA fusion to detect surface anomalies smaller than 0.5 meters, while Weather Monitoring (Use Case 5) repurposes synchronisation signals for localised atmospheric sensing. For smart home applications, Fall Detection (Use Case 7) leverages the system's 50Hz update rate and 10ms latency to enable rapid emergency response. Overall, by optimising the CRB-SINR trade-off, the proposed framework dynamically manages resource allocation to meet the unique KPI requirements across all use cases.

The main activity of this task introduces an innovative transmit signalling design and resource allocation framework for D-JCAS systems, integrating both colocated and distributed MIMO radar for target localisation alongside noncoherent CoMP downlink communication. The sensing component adopts a hybrid localisation strategy that combines AOA and TOF measurements, effectively leveraging the strengths of both techniques to enable high-precision target localisation.

7.2 System Model

Next-generation wireless networks are increasingly converging communication and radar sensing functionalities within a unified infrastructure, a paradigm known as JCAS, which promises significant gains in spectral and hardware efficiency [67]. When multiple JCAS nodes collaborate over a wide geographical area, they form a D-JCAS architecture, as illustrated in Figure 7.1 [68]. This distributed setup introduces new challenges, including the management of inter-cell communication interference and the coordination of radar sensing tasks across spatially separated antennas. In the absence of phase synchronisation (i.e., noncoherent operation), the waveforms transmitted by individual nodes combine in power rather than amplitude, which can significantly impact both communication and sensing performance.

We consider N JCAS nodes, each equipped with M_t transmit antennas and M_r receive antennas, deployed over a region. A CU handles the distribution of downlink data to each node as well as the processing of radar returns. Communication takes place on the downlink to U single-antenna users, while the radar functionality seeks to localize up to K targets in two-dimensional space. The nodes

operate in full-duplex mode, transmitting and receiving simultaneously on OFDM subcarriers. Time-frequency synchronisation among nodes is assumed, ensuring alignment of OFDM symbols across the network. However, there is no phase-level synchronisation. Consequently, signals from different nodes cannot be coherently combined, resulting in a power-adding effect at each user or radar receiver. Each node's position is denoted $\mathbf{p}_n = [x_n, y_n]^T$, and the user positions are $\mathbf{q}_u = [x_u, y_u]^T$. The goal is twofold: ensure that each user's SINR surpasses a threshold Γ_c , while also minimizing the localisation error for the K targets.

Figure 7.1: Illustration of the D-JCAS system.

The transmit signal at node n during OFDM symbol t combines both communication waveforms and radar waveforms. We write:

$$\mathbf{X}_n[t] = \mathbf{X}_{\{c,n\}}[t] + \mathbf{X}_{\{s,n\}}[t]. \quad (7.1)$$

Here, $\mathbf{X}_{\{c,n\}}[t]$ is the communication signal intended for multiple users on L subcarriers, while $\mathbf{X}_{\{s,n\}}[t]$ is the radar signal designed to facilitate target detection and localisation. For the communication portion, each subcarrier l can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{x}_{\{c,n,l\}} = \mathbf{W}_{\{c,n,l\}} \mathbf{s}_{\{c,l\}}, \quad (7.2)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_{\{c,n,l\}}$ in $\mathbb{C}^{M_t \times U}$ is the precoding matrix for U users, and $\mathbf{s}_{\{c,l\}}$ in $\mathbb{C}^{U \times 1}$ is the data symbol vector. The node's radar signal $\mathbf{X}_{\{s,n\}}$ may also be distributed across the L subcarriers, potentially employing orthogonal waveforms per antenna to achieve diversity in angle and range estimation. Node n thus sends a composite signal that satisfies certain power constraints on each antenna. Due to phase noncoherency, the power from each node accumulates rather than the amplitudes. This affects the final expressions for the SINR and for the FIM used in radar localisation, as subsequent sections describe.

1) Communication SINR

For user u on subcarrier l , define $\mathbf{h}_{\{n,u,l\}} \in \mathbb{C}^{M_t \times 1}$ as the channel from node n to that user. Let $\mathbf{w}_{\{c,n,u,l\}}$ be the beam corresponding to user u in the precoding matrix $\mathbf{W}_{\{c,n,l\}}$. The SINR accounts for the intended signal power, the interference from other users on the same subcarrier, the interference

from radar signals, and AWGN. Under noncoherent combination, the useful signal power from multiple nodes sums in power, leading to:

$$\gamma_{\{c,u,l\}} = \frac{\left(\sum_{n=1}^N |\mathbf{h}_{\{n,u,l\}}^H \mathbf{w}_{\{c,n,u,l\}}|^2\right)}{\left(\sum_{n=1}^N \left[\sum_{i \neq u} |\mathbf{h}_{\{n,u,l\}}^H \mathbf{w}_{\{c,n,i,l\}}|^2 + |\mathbf{h}_{\{n,u,l\}}^H \mathbf{x}_{\{s,n,l\}}|^2 \right] + \frac{\sigma_c^2}{L}\right)} \quad (7.3)$$

Note that radar signal interference from node n enters via the term $|\mathbf{h}_{\{n,u,l\}}^H \mathbf{x}_{\{s,n,l\}}|^2$. The sum of these terms across all N nodes constitutes the total interference. Maintaining $\gamma_{\{c,u,l\}} \geq \Gamma_c$ for each user u and each subcarrier l is a principal design requirement. We must control the radar waveforms so as not to degrade communication performance below acceptable QoS levels.

2) Radar Localisation Accuracy via CRB

The radar localisation performance is quantified by the CRB, which characterizes the minimum achievable mean square error of the target parameter estimates. The target localisation is achieved by exploiting both TOF and AOA estimation as shown in Figure 7.2. If we collect all unknown parameters, target positions and reflection coefficients, into a vector Θ , the for an observation \mathbf{Y}_s forms the basis for computing the CRB:

$$\text{CRB} = \text{tr}([\mathbf{F}(\Theta)]^{-1}). \quad (7.4)$$

A lower CRB indicates more accurate target localisation. In a noncoherent distributed radar configuration, monostatic and bistatic links from all N nodes can be utilised, improving spatial diversity. However, the noncoherent nature modifies the relationship between the radar signals and the received reflections, thus affecting how the FIM is formulated. In essence, the cross-correlation between different nodes' waveforms does not translate into coherent combining but can still impart beneficial diversity for target localisation.

Figure 7.2: Target localization methods in D-JCAS: (a) TOF-based localization and (b) AOA-based localization.

7.3 Algorithm Description

The goal of the design is to minimise the CRB while ensuring each user's SINR remains above a threshold. Additionally, we impose a per-antenna power limit on each node's transmit antennas. A typical formulation of the problem is :

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{minimize } \text{tr}([\mathbf{F}(\Theta)]^{-1}), \\ & \text{s. t. } \gamma_{\{c,u,l\}} \geq \Gamma_c, \\ & \quad [\mathbf{R}_n]_{\{m,m\}} \leq P_T. \end{aligned} \quad (7.5)$$

Here, $\mathbf{F}(\Theta)$ depends on the design of the waveforms, which influences both power and cross-correlation properties for radar sensing. Meanwhile, $\gamma_{\{c,u,l\}}$ depends on $\mathbf{x}_{\{c,n,l\}}$, the communication

precoding. Because $\mathbf{x}_{\{s,n,l\}}$ and $\mathbf{x}_{\{c,n,l\}}$ share the same power budget, these signals must be allocated in a manner that balances sensing and communication demands. For D-JCAS signalling design, we give three different signalling designs depending on signal structures: optimal, orthogonal, and beamforming designs. They are investigated as follows:

1) Optimal Design (P.1)

The optimal design imposes no restrictions on how each node's radar and communication waveforms correlate across subcarriers. This means that cross-node and cross-subcarrier correlations can be exploited in principle. In an SDR approach, the design variables become large power spectral density (PSD) blocks capturing the communication and radar signal covariances for every node and subcarrier. Because the system is noncoherent, each user's SINR sums power terms from multiple nodes independently, whereas the FIM for radar incorporates cross-node correlations if waveforms are correlated. Solving this yields the theoretical best CRB under the constraints. However, the high dimensionality of PSD matrices can make (P.1) computationally expensive. After a solver obtains a solution, a rank-1 factorisation step is needed to extract individual beam vectors for each user and subcarrier.

2) Orthogonal Design (P.2)

The orthogonal design reduces complexity by enforcing subcarrier orthogonality among nodes. Specifically, node n is assigned a subset of subcarriers that do not overlap with those assigned to node $m \neq n$. A common technique is subcarrier interleaving. This ensures that cross-node signal correlations vanish across subcarriers, simplifying both the communication SINR constraints and the radar FIM computations. Consequently, the design variables for each node's subcarrier become decoupled from those of other nodes. The resulting semidefinite program is smaller in size and can often be solved more readily. While orthogonal design may sacrifice some potential benefits of cross-node cooperation in radar, it retains many advantages of distributing multiple nodes and typically achieves near-optimal CRB for moderate setups. Moreover, rank-1 extraction is less complicated, as each subcarrier is handled largely in isolation.

3) Beamforming Design (P.3)

The beamforming design further reduces complexity by imposing uniform radar beamforming across all subcarriers within each node. Instead of independently optimizing radar signals per subcarrier, node n uses a fixed beamforming matrix for its radar signal across the entire bandwidth. The motivation is that AOA estimation primarily relies on spatial shaping, while TOF estimation is not optimised in this design. Consequently, the CRB generally worsens in terms of range accuracy. However, the gain in computational complexity can be substantial, as we only optimise one radar beam per node, rather than one per node-subcarrier pair. This approach can be effective in systems where angle estimation is paramount, and range resolution can be tolerated at a coarser level.

Overall, the choice among these three depends on system requirements (precision vs. complexity), the range of expected target positions, and the number of users or subcarriers. In many practical scenarios, orthogonal design (P.2) strikes a good balance, although some deployments prioritize the simplest beamforming approach, while others can afford the fully optimal method for maximum sensing performance

7.4 Results

First, we validate the CRB-SINR trade-offs of the three designs, as shown in Figure 7.3 (a). The proposed D-JCAS transmit signal designs clearly demonstrate trade-offs between sensing and communication performance. As expected, the optimal signal design (P.1) achieves the best sensing performance compared to the other two designs utilizing orthogonal signal transmission. This result indicates that orthogonal signals for distributed MIMO radar do not guarantee optimal sensing performance for target localisation. Furthermore, the overall JCAS performance degrades as the

number of users increases in all three designs, and the maximum achievable communication SINR also decreases. Figure 7.3 (b), illustrates the JCAS performance gain of D-JCAS with varying numbers of cooperative nodes. Here, the JCAS nodes are positioned all equidistant from the origin. As the number of cooperative nodes increases, we observe improvements in both sensing and communication performance. From the perspective of communication performance, this cooperation gain stems from noncoherent CoMP transmission, which leverages the power combining gain of distributed JCAS nodes. For target localisation, the performance gain arises from the noncoherent processing of the distributed MIMO radar, utilising TOF measurements to localise the target [69]. It is worth noting that this cooperative sensing gain is significantly influenced by the geometry of the target and node positions [3]. Furthermore, the optimal number of distributed JCAS nodes can be determined by considering the antenna-to-node allocation for a given cooperative node density.

Figure 7.3: JCAS trade-off of the signaling designs with varying numbers of (a) users and (b) nodes..

Figure 7.4: Comparisons of the execution time to the number of subcarriers.

We empirically evaluate the execution time of each D-JCAS transmit signal design. The measured execution times are averaged over 100 trials. As shown in Figure 7.4, for all three design methods, the execution time increases with the number of subcarriers, consistent with the complexity trends. As expected, the optimal signal design (P.1) exhibits the longest execution time among the three designs. The three designs demonstrate clear trade-offs between performance and complexity. Consequently, one can select an appropriate design based on the system requirements, such as computational resources.

Figure 7.5: Performance gain of D-JCAS with various synchronisation approaches.

D-JCAS improves target localisation by leveraging spatial diversity in distributed MIMO radar but is sensitive to synchronisation errors. Figure 7.5 compares noncoherent D-JCAS with a single-node JCAS system. When using the same number of antennas per node, D-JCAS achieves better localisation accuracy and SINR due to power combining. However, a single-node JCAS system with an equivalent total number of antennas attains higher SINR due to coherent gain. While D-JCAS benefits from spatial diversity, poor time synchronization (250 ps accuracy) prevents it from outperforming the single-node system. In contrast, the improved synchronization (10 ps accuracy) provides enough cooperative sensing gain even with the decentralised processing.

7.5 Future Work

Future work in signal design and resource optimization will explore coherent D-JCAS systems, where distributed nodes achieve phase-level synchronisation, enabling their signals to combine coherently at both communication receivers and radar front-ends [70]. Coherent operation promises further improvements in communication throughput and radar parameter estimation accuracy. However, achieving and maintaining precise phase alignment across geographically dispersed antennas poses significant challenges. Addressing phase noise and ensuring stable synchronisation under dynamic conditions will require advanced phase-tracking algorithms, meticulous hardware calibration, and robust synchronisation protocols.

Another promising direction is the development of efficient decentralised signalling strategies that reduce reliance on a central processing unit. While centralised approaches can globally optimise signal design, they introduce considerable overhead in terms of data exchange, computational complexity, and latency. In contrast, decentralised methods enable nodes to make local decisions based on partial or shared information, coordinating their sensing and communication resources independently. This distributed architecture could improve scalability, reduce signalling overhead, and offer greater resilience to node failures. However, it introduces new challenges in maintaining near-optimal performance amid asynchronous operations and limited global knowledge.

8 Node Association for Scalable Cell-Free Systems

8.1 Motivation and Objectives

CF JCAS has recently gained significant attention due to its potential to enhance sensing performance by leveraging the macro-diversity and coverage benefits of densely distributed APs. However, most existing works assume that all APs serve all users, which leads to scalability and implementation challenges. To address this, a shift toward clustering designs has been proposed, where more efficient resource allocation, such as node association, can reduce signaling overhead and improve scalability. In the JCAS domain, few works have tackled this problem [60]-[62]. In [60], the authors propose an AP mode selection and beamforming strategy where each AP dynamically operates as a transmitter or receiver. The work in [61] fixes the set of transmitting and receiving APs but introduces an algorithm to select APs for either communication or sensing functions, along with power control. User-centric (UC) CF, for JCAS scenarios, is introduced in [62], where the authors propose a joint waveform and clustering design that creates user-centric clusters, with each UE served by a subset of APs.

However, the problem of clustering design for UC-CF multistatic JCAS has not been previously studied. In this scenario, unlike [62], the receiver APs are distinct from the transmitter APs, which provides greater flexibility and spatial diversity for target detection.

This work aligns with the objectives of Task 4.4, which focuses on intelligent resource allocation methods and the self-organization of CF radio sensing. In this context, we study algorithms for associating sets of APs to UEs in an JCAS scenario, where the transmitter APs communicate with multiple UEs and simultaneously steer beams toward a target. First, we propose a simple association scheme in which AP-UE pairing is performed randomly. The second algorithm uses the channel norm as a metric to perform the association between APs and UEs. Finally, the third scheme assigns a fixed number of UEs—with the highest channel norms, to each AP. It is worth noting that this work presents preliminary results on intelligent resource allocation, and optimized methods are foreseen for following reports.

The proposed resource allocation methods for CF ISAC scenarios contribute to several 6G-MUSICAL use cases, particularly those requiring energy-efficient and scalable network designs. By leveraging CF networks, the intelligent association of APs and UEs reduces fronthaul load, optimizes power consumption, and lowers the computational complexity of the algorithms. These improvements are especially relevant in dynamic environments where real-time sensing and communication need to be jointly optimized. In particular, the indoor localisation of AGVs in warehouses and production facilities (Use Case 6.1.1 in D2.1) stands out as a key application, where intelligent AP-UE association reduces fronthaul load and ensures low-latency, high-accuracy positioning in complex and dynamic indoor environments. Similarly, smart convoy (Use Case 6.1.2 in D2.1) operations benefit from efficient AP clustering and beam steering, enabling coordinated movement and communication across multiple vehicles while minimizing energy consumption. Intruder detection in secure areas (Use Case 6.2.1 in D2.1) and UAV intrusion detection (Use Case 6.2.3 in D2.1) are also closely aligned with this work, as they require reliable and flexible sensing infrastructures capable of adapting to variable threat locations. In such scenarios, the separation of transmitter and receiver APs in a multistatic CF ISAC setup, combined with optimized association algorithms, enhances spatial coverage and target detection performance while keeping computational complexity low.

8.2 System Model

Figure 8.1 displays a UC-CF ISAC scenario comprising M transmitters (AP_{tx}), N receivers (AP_{rx}), and K UEs. In this UC-CF scenario, the k th UE is served by a subset of the total M AP_{tx} . Specifically, the set $\mathcal{M}_k \subset \{AP_{tx,1}, \dots, AP_{tx,M}\}$ denotes the group of APs assigned to serve the k th UE. Simultaneously, the M AP_{tx} steers radio-sensing probing beams towards an area of interest.

This work considers that the set of AP_{rx} is configured to function exclusively as radio-sensing receivers. Specifically, the signals received by the AP_{rx} are processed to detect and estimate objects in the environment. In addition, it is assumed that APs are synchronized and that the CSI between the AP_{tx} and the UEs is perfectly known by the AP_{tx} .

Figure 8.1: Illustration of the considered UC-CF ISAC scenario.

A. Transmitted Signal Model

This work considers downlink transmission, where the m th AP_{tx} transmits data towards a set of UEs, defined as $\mathcal{K}_m \subset \{UE_1, \dots, UE_K\}$. More specifically, each AP_{tx} transmits data towards the set of UEs \mathcal{K}_m , where the communication data streams are also used for radio-sensing purposes. The signal transmitted by the m th AP_{tx} is expressed as

$$\mathbf{x}_m = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_m} \mathbf{f}_{m,k} s_k \quad (8.1)$$

where $\mathbf{f}_{m,k} \in C^{N_{tx}}$ represents the beamforming vector corresponding to the k th data stream. The power budget for the beamforming vector is constrained by P_m , formally

$$\|\mathbf{F}_m\|_F^2 \leq P_m. \quad (8.2)$$

B. Communication Model

As previously mentioned, the transmission of communication data follows an UC-CF approach. Consequently, the signal received by the k th UE is modeled as the sum of the signals transmitted by the M AP_{tx} . The received signal y_k is given by

$$y_k = \underbrace{\sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_k} \mathbf{h}_{m,k}^H \mathbf{f}_{m,k} s_k}_{\text{Desired Signal (DS)}} + \underbrace{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_i} \mathbf{h}_{m,k}^H \mathbf{f}_{m,i} s_i}_{\text{Multi-user Interference (MUI)}} + \underbrace{n_k}_{\text{Noise}} \quad (8.3)$$

where, $\mathcal{K} = \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$ represent the total number of UEs, and $n_k \sim \text{CN}(0, \sigma_k^2)$ represents complex additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) with zero mean and variance σ_k^2 . The term $\mathbf{h}_{m,k} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{tx}}}$ denotes the communication channel between the m th AP_{tx} and the k th UE.

C. Radio-Sensing Model

A multi-static topology is considered in this work, where the M AP_{tx}s steer radio-sensing probing beams toward a desired area, and N AP_{rx}s collect the echoes reflected from a target. It is assumed that a LoS path exists both from the AP_{tx} to the target and from the target to the AP_{rx}. Therefore, the channel between the m -th AP_{tx} and the n th AP_{rx} consists of a single path [1], as shown in Figure 8.1. The signal received at the n th AP_{rx} can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{y}_n = \sum_m \hat{\alpha}_{m,n} \mathbf{a}_{N_{\text{rx}}}(\phi_n) \mathbf{a}_{N_{\text{tx}}}^H(\theta_m) \mathbf{x}_m + \mathbf{n}_n \quad (8.4)$$

where $\hat{\alpha}_{m,n}$ represents the path gain, including the radar cross section (RCS) of the target [1]. The variables θ_m and ϕ_n represent the AoD from the m th AP_{tx} and the angle of arrival AoA at the n th AP_{rx}, respectively.

8.3 Algorithm Description

The algorithms developed in this work represent initial research toward more optimal methods for AP–UE association in CF ISAC scenarios. These methods are designed to associate APs to UEs while balancing coverage and connectivity constraints. It is important to note that all algorithms assume the association step is performed prior to beamforming/precoder design, which can later follow the methodology outlined in Section 0 of this deliverable. Three algorithms are presented below.

Algorithm 1: Random Association

Let $\mathcal{M} = \{1, \dots, M\}$ be the set of AP indices. The algorithm constructs the binary association matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \{0, 1\}^{M \times K}$, where the entry $a_{m,k} = 1$ if m th AP_{tx} is associated with the k th UE.

1. For each $k \in \mathcal{K}$, randomly select one AP $m \in \mathcal{M}$, and set $a_{m,k} \leftarrow 1$ to ensure each UE is served.
2. For each $m \in \mathcal{M}$ not yet associated with any UE, randomly assign a $k \in \mathcal{K}$ such that $a_{m,k} \leftarrow 1$, ensuring every AP is active.
3. Add random AP–UE pairs (m,k) with $a_{m,k} \leftarrow 1$ until the total number of active associations equals a target number N_{conn} .

Algorithm 2: Channel Norm-Based Association

This algorithm exploits channel quality to guide the association based on the norm $\|\mathbf{h}_{m,k}\|$ of the communication channel between m th AP k th UE.

1. Compute all channel norms $\|\mathbf{h}_{m,k}\|$ for $(m,k) \in \mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{K}$.
2. For each AP $m \in \mathcal{M}$, associate it with the UE having the highest channel norm: $k^* = \underset{k}{\text{argmax}} \|\mathbf{h}_{m,k}\|$; set $a_{m,k^*} \leftarrow 1$.
3. For each UE $k \in \mathcal{K}$ not yet served, associate it with the AP with the strongest channel: $m^* = \underset{m}{\text{argmax}} \|\mathbf{h}_{m,k}\|$; set $a_{m^*,k} \leftarrow 1$.
4. Sort all remaining AP–UE pairs by decreasing $\|\mathbf{h}_{m,k}\|$ and assign them until $\sum a_{m,k} = N_{\text{conn}}$.

Algorithm 3: Channel Norm Based with Equal Number of UEs per AP Association

This algorithm constrains the number of UEs associated per AP and uses the channel norm for

prioritization.

1. Set the target number of UEs per AP as $N_{UE}^{per-AP} = N_{conn}/M$.
2. Compute all channel norms $\|\mathbf{h}_{m,k}\|$ for $(m,k) \in \mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{K}$.
3. For each UE $k \in \mathcal{K}$, find its best AP: $m^* = \underset{m}{\operatorname{argmax}} \|\mathbf{h}_{m,k}\|$; set $a_{m^*,k} \leftarrow 1$.
4. For each AP $m \in \mathcal{M}$, assign it to its top N_{UE}^{per-AP} UEs with the highest $\|\mathbf{h}_{m,k}\|$, avoiding duplicate assignments.

8.4 Results

This section is dedicated to evaluating the algorithms introduced in Section 8.3. Specifically, these are:

- Algorithm 1, referred to as RandAssoc;
- Algorithm 2, referred to as NormAssoc;
- Algorithm 3, referred to as NormPerApAssoc.

The precoder design employed to generate the results presented here follows the approach detailed in Section 2, as previously discussed. The following results were obtained for a scenario with $M = 4$ AP_{tx}, $N = 2$ AP_{rx}, and $K = 4$ UEs. Both AP_{tx} and AP_{rx} are equipped with ULAs consisting of $N_{tx} = 32$ and $N_{rx} = 32$ antenna elements, respectively, spaced by $\lambda/2$. The noise variance at the AP_{rx}s is set to $\sigma_n^2 = -20$ dB. For simplicity, we assume that the variance of $\hat{\alpha}_{m,n} \forall m, n$ is $\sigma_{m,n}^2 = -10$ dB. Lastly, the power budget for the distributed beamforming matrices is set to $P_m = 1 \forall m$.

Figure 8.2 presents a comparison illustrating the trade-off between the mean sum of SINRs and the sSNR constraint Δ (refer to Section 2 for more details). The sum of the SINRs is computed for Δ values ranging from 28 to 42 dB. Each data point represents the average over 400 independent random realisations of the communication channels. In this experiment, the performance of the three proposed algorithms is compared against the baseline classical CF association, where each AP serves all UEs simultaneously. The comparison is carried out under different AP-UE connectivity constraints, specifically for $N_{conn} \in \{8, 12\}$, representing the number of active AP-UE connections selected out of a total of 16 possible.

Figure 8.2: Comparison of the Sum of SINRs vs. Δ for CF-ISAC with $M=4$, $N=2$, and $K=4$.

The result in Figure 8.2 illustrates that the UC-CF approaches, RandAssoc, NormAssoc, and NormPerApAssoc, exhibit lower performance compared to the classical CF association, where all APs serve all UEs without connectivity constraints. In addition, among the UC-CF schemes, NormAssoc achieves the best performance. This is because RandAssoc randomly assigns AP-UE connections without using any channel information, while NormPerApAssoc, although it leverages channel norms, imposes an additional constraint by limiting the number of connections per. In contrast, NormAssoc selects connections based purely on the strongest channel norms across all AP-UE pairs, providing greater flexibility in optimising the association. Finally, it is observed that as the total number of allowed AP-UE connections increases, the performance gap between the different UC-CF algorithms narrows. This is expected, as looser connectivity constraints allow each algorithm more freedom to approximate the behaviour of the full classical CF association.

8.5 Future Work

Future work will focus on the development of more advanced yet low-complexity AP-UE association algorithms. There is potential to explore more refined heuristics that leverage additional channel or network structure information while keeping complexity manageable for distributed implementation. Another important direction is the joint optimisation of the AP-UE association matrix A and the precoding vectors. Finally, an extension of this work is to investigate target-centric association strategies for the sensing functionality, analogous to the UC-CF approach in communications. In this case, the objective would be to associate subsets of APs to specific sensing objectives.

9 Conclusions

This document presents the initial outcomes of Task 4.3 and Task 4.4 within WP4 of the 6G-MUSICAL project. The project focused on developing algorithms for multistatic sensing, baseband algorithms at the sensing stations, resource allocation algorithms, transmit signalling design, and algorithms for associating sets of APs to UEs in a cell-free scenario. The work addressed key challenges of accuracy, scalability, and cost-effectiveness in next-generation wireless networks.

Specifically, a two-stage beamforming algorithm was designed to reduce fronthaul load by distributing signal processing between the CU and APs. This algorithm jointly considers communication and sensing requirements, explicitly handling power and SNR constraints in a cell-free joint communication and sensing framework. We also explored multistatic sensing algorithms based on OFDM, emphasising transmitter and receiver beamforming as well as range, Doppler, AoA estimation, time synchronisation, and translation into global Cartesian coordinates.

Our findings confirm that conventional communication nodes are unsuitable as sensing stations due to limited resolution caused by communication-centric optimisation. To address this, we proposed a new architectural design and processing algorithms for single-station operation, enabling high-resolution data collection and secure sensing, both critical for centralised multistatic sensing. Simulations and experiments using a modified OpenWiFi platform (full-stack 802.11 FPGA implementation) validated the effectiveness of the proposed methods.

We further examined Doppler and angle-of-arrival estimation for passive objects using noisy multi-time-instance signals. The framework supports both local processing at sensing nodes and centralised fusion. The analysis highlights how system parameters, such as the number of APs and time samples, affect estimation accuracy. Additionally, three resource-sharing strategies were compared in terms of Cramér–Rao bounds for AoA and symbol estimation under unitary normalised constant-envelope signalling. These results provide engineering insights and benchmarks for practical algorithms in use cases like intruder detection and unauthorised UAV localisation.

An innovative transmit signalling and resource allocation framework for distributed JCAS was also proposed, integrating both colocated and distributed MIMO radar for target localisation alongside noncoherent CoMP downlink communication. The sensing component adopts a hybrid localisation strategy that combines AoA and TOF measurements, effectively leveraging the strengths of both techniques to enable high-precision target localisation. Finally, we discussed algorithms for associating sets of APs to UEs in a JCAS scenario, where the transmitter APs communicate with multiple UEs and simultaneously steer beams toward a target. First, we proposed a simple association scheme in which AP–UE pairing is performed randomly. The second algorithm uses the channel norm as a metric to perform the association between APs and UEs, while the third one assigns a fixed number of UEs, with the highest channel norms to each AP.

Overall, these contributions establish the foundation for advanced multistatic sensing in the 6G-MUSICAL project, supporting high-accuracy positioning, 3D imaging and object identification. The work demonstrated significant progress in resource allocation and self-organisation mechanisms, paving the way toward more reliable and high-performance 6G systems.

10 References

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